

In Search of New Geometries for Probing Spin-Spin Interactions

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Abstract

Finding evidence for new long range spin-spin interactions (LRSSIs) would mean the discovery of exciting new physics. In two of our recent papers [1, 2] we have demonstrated a new geophysical method to probe for LRSSIs using our dual Cs-Hg co-magnetometer experiment at Amherst College. In this thesis, we present the results of efforts to explore new optical geometries to upgrade the previous generation of the apparatus, the key improvement of which is having the pumping and probing lasers be orthogonal to the magnetic field. We explore two different schemes of running the experiment: the pump-then-probe (PTP) scheme and the continuous pumping and probing (CPP) scheme, using only Cs atomic vapor cells. We determine that both schemes have a statistical noise level roughly an order of magnitude below our sensitivity goal of $\Delta v_N^{\text{Cs}} < 32 \mu\text{Hz}$. We present results of investigations of systematic effects that arise from shifts in the intensity and frequency of the pump and probe lasers. We find that as expected, PTP has smaller systematic uncertainties and at this point is the more likely scheme to be used in the future.

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Chapter 1

Theoretical Motivations

In this thesis, we shall be chiefly concerned with exotic long-range spin-spin interactions (LRSSIs), or long-range interactions arising between two spin-polarized particles. Spin-spin interactions are not completely alien to our everyday experiences with physics. In fact, some forms of electromagnetism, the interaction responsible for things like friction and electricity, consist of spin-spin interactions. For example, the potential arising from the interaction of two magnetic dipoles takes the form [3]

$$V = \frac{\mu_0 \mu_B^2 g^2}{4\pi r^3 \hbar^2} (\boldsymbol{\sigma}_1 \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_2 - 3(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_1 \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}})(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_2 \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}})), \quad (1.1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_1$ and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_2$ are the spins of the two particles involved,

$\hat{\mathbf{r}}$ is the unit vector parallel to the line connecting them,

μ_0 is the magnetic permeability,

μ_B is the Bohr magneton,

g is the g-factor of the two particles, and

\hbar is Planck's constant divided by 2π .

However, this thesis is not mainly concerned with standard spin-spin interactions like Eq. 1.1 above. Instead, we are interested in experimentally probing interactions that are completely removed from the four standard forces that are established to exist in nature: gravity, the weak force, electromagnetism, and the strong force, thus earning the label of “exotic” interactions. If evidence for such interactions is found, these would constitute a fifth force of nature. This would be an exciting form of new physics. The question remains, however, why should we be concerned with exotic interactions? How did this interest arise, and what is its relevance to the enterprise of physics research as a whole? To answer this question, we must briefly look back to the history of physics, especially in the last few decades.

1.1 Matter, Interactions, and the Emergence of the Standard Model

Physics is a science studying the nature and behavior of matter in the universe. One of the most obvious aspects of studying the behavior of matter is studying the possible interactions between different bodies of matter, such as why a projectile seems to always drop back to the ground when a human throws it up. Unsurprisingly, throughout its history, much of physics has been concerned with the study of forces which give rise to these interactions. It started with Newton, who came up with a rigorous theory that explained the gravitational force. In the process, he discovered his Three Laws of Motion. In

the 19th century, one of the main scientific achievements was Maxwell's unification of electricity and magnetism. The resulting theory of electromagnetism constitutes a second force in nature.

The progress of physics in the 20th century continued with the discoveries of two pillars of modern physics: relativity and quantum mechanics. Both of these theories were the subject of Einstein's remarkable *annus mirabilis* of 1905, when he published papers on special relativity [4] and the photoelectric effect [5]. In the next few years, Einstein developed the theory of general relativity (GR) [6], which unified Newtonian gravity and special relativity. Up to the current day, GR remains the only experimentally verified theory that successfully describes gravity. Meanwhile, Einstein's argument for the existence of light quanta in the photoelectric effect was vindicated in 1923, with Compton's scattering experiments that established the existence of the photon, the force carrier for electromagnetism. Einstein's argument, together with Max Planck's theory of quantized electromagnetic radiation (1900) and Bohr's initial model of the hydrogen atom (1913), eventually developed into quantum mechanics (QM) in the 1920s, which has since been the predominant paradigm in physics concerning interactions on a small scale.

This theme of unifying our understanding of different interactions continued in the next few decades. The discovery of QM led to interest in how to unify it with the well-known theory of electromagnetism. In 1929, Pauli and Heisenberg came up with the first attempts at quantum electrodynamics (QED), a theory that described electromagnetism in the language of QM. These first attempts came up short, in particular giving an infinite value for

the energy of the electron in its own electromagnetic field [7]. In the post-World War II era physicists resumed work on QED, culminating with the Nobel Prize in Physics being awarded for in 1965 to Feynman, Tomonaga, and Schwinger for their development of the theory. QED was the first example of a quantum field theory (QFT), a field theory that seeks to explain a force in terms of quantum mechanics. The success of QED has been confirmed up to the present day by experiments such as those measuring the electron g -factor, the most recent of which found an agreement with the QED-calculated value to almost a part per trillion [8].

Meanwhile, various events had led to the discovery of the weak force. Pauli first proposed the neutrino (which he then called the “neutron”) in 1930 as a way to explain the puzzling phenomenon of beta decay. In the following year, Fermi created the first theory of beta decay that incorporated this new particle, the experimental confirmation of which did not occur until 1959. After the success of QED, theorists sought to create a successful QFT that explained the weak force. However, early attempts were unsuccessful, and many physicists abandoned QFT in the 1960s in favor of doing research about Chew’s S -matrix theory [7]. Thus when Glashow (1961) [9] and Weinberg and Salam (1967) [10] found a way to combine electromagnetism and the weak interaction in the framework of a field theory, now known as electroweak theory, it was initially largely ignored until the 1970s. The trio’s work was eventually awarded with the Nobel Prize in Physics in 1979. In this theory, intermediate vector bosons were proposed as the force carriers for the weak force, consisting of the W^+ , W^- , and Z bosons. Direct evidence of their existence was obtained

in 1983 [11].

These advances in theoretical physics were accompanied and often initiated by many groundbreaking experimental discoveries in particle physics. This began in 1897 with the discovery of the electron by J.J. Thompson, followed by Rutherford's gold foil experiments that discovered the structure of the atom in 1911. The fundamental question of how multiple positively charged protons could remain in the nucleus of an atom without repelling each other resulted in theorists positing the existence of the strong force. A string of discoveries over the next few decades established that the proton and electron were not the only elementary particles that existed: the positron (1931), neutron (1932), muon and pion (1947), neutral kaons (1947), charged kaons (1949), and the antiproton and antineutron (1955), among others [11].

Many of these particles had been predicted by theorists, such as the pion, which was proposed by Yukawa in 1934 as the carrier particle of the strong force. Some others, like the muon, were completely unexpected. To classify the various new particles that had been discovered, in 1961 Gell-Mann came up with a scheme known as the Eightfold Way, which classified particles based on the properties of charge and strangeness. To explain the Eightfold Way, Gell-Mann proposed the quark model in 1964. This theory proposed that baryons and mesons are made up of elementary constituents known as quarks, and that different kinds of elementary particles are the result of quarks with different properties combining together. While there has been no direct observation of free quarks, the existence of many new particles predicted by the theory has been vindicated, most famously in the discovery of the J/ψ meson in 1974 by

Ting and Richter [12, 13]. These developments in the quark model led to Gell-Mann and Harald Fritzsch proposing the theory of quantum chromodynamics (QCD) in 1972, a QFT describing strong interactions. This theory posited gluons as the force carrier for the strong force [14]. By the 1980s, the various theories created and confirmed over the years had converged into the Standard Model, which classified all the different elementary particles: leptons, quarks, force carrier bosons, and the Higgs boson. The Standard Model's latest triumph is the experimental discovery of the Higgs boson at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) in 2012 [15, 16].

While it has been shown to be experimentally robust, the Standard Model suffers from the limitation of requiring over 20 arbitrary parameters that are theoretically unexplained and whose value is only obtainable by experiment. We have seen from the history of physics that the quest of understanding the interactions of matter in nature entails finding a theory to unify all four forces, including harmonizing quantum mechanics and general relativity. The Standard Model, therefore, falls short of being a “final theory” of physics and invites opportunities for further investigation by physicists of this and future generations. String theory is one of the most studied candidates for such a final theory. It proposes that all matter consists of elementary microscopic strings, and that the different particles are different modes of vibrations of such strings. However, to this day there has been no experimental evidence for string theory, and little realistic prospect of being able to perform an experiment capable of probing it in the near future [17].

1.2 Origins of Exotic LRSSIs

1.2.1 The First Spin-Spin Interactions: The Strong-CP Problem and Axions

Non-electromagnetic spin-spin interactions were first proposed due to the strong-CP problem. This arose from the study of whether the laws of physics are symmetrical. The main fundamental discrete symmetries physicists are concerned with are charge (C), parity (P), and time (T) symmetry. For a long time, it was assumed that parity symmetry (which can be thought of as left- or right-handedness) was self-evident in physics, and there was experimental evidence that this was true for the case of strong, electromagnetic, and gravitational interactions. However, in 1956 Lee and Yang proposed their theory of parity violation in weak interactions [18], which was experimentally verified by Wu the following year [19]. While parity symmetry had definitely been found to be violated in Wu's experiment, CP-symmetry (combining both charge and parity symmetry) was not, and physicists began to wonder whether CP-symmetry was a "true" symmetry in nature [11]. But in 1964 Cronin and Fitch found evidence of CP violation in their experiments involving neutral kaons [20].

In contrast to the ample evidence for CP violation in the weak force, the strong-CP problem emerges from the lack of evidence for such violations in the strong force. The theory of QCD describing the strong force allows for a CP-violating term in the QCD Lagrangian, which is characterized by a parameter commonly denoted as θ_{qcd} . One of the best ways to probe θ_{qcd} is by measuring the electric dipole moment d_n of the neutron. A non-zero value would indicate

strong CP violation [21]. However, various searches have only found a value of zero, with the latest one constraining it at [22]

$$|d_n| < 2.9 \times 10^{-26} e \cdot cm, \quad (1.2)$$

leading to the corresponding tight constraint

$$|\theta_{\text{QCD}}| \lesssim 10^{-10}, \quad (1.3)$$

hence giving us the strong-CP problem. Various theories have been proposed to explain the lack of such CP violation, with one of the most notable by Roberto Peccei and Helen Quinn [23]. Peccei-Quinn theory proposes the existence of an axion field a functioning as a parameter of θ_{QCD} . This results in the CP-violating term being canceled out from the QCD Lagrangian. The axion, the new particle that mediates this field, is a pseudoscalar boson, which simply means that it is a boson with spin-0 and odd parity.¹ It is characterized by an axion decay constant f_a that determines the strength of the axion's interaction with Standard Model particles. For a large value of f_a , the interaction will be very weak, making the axion an example of a Weakly Interacting Sub-eV Particle (WISP) [21].

In 1984, partly motivated by the proposal of not just axions, but also other hypothetical particles such as familons, majorons, arions, and spin-1 antigravitons, Moody and Wilczek investigated the the potential forces that could arise from the exchange from spin-0 bosons [24]. They investigated both

¹A scalar boson is just a boson with spin-0 and even parity.

scalar and pseudoscalar bosons, and found spin-dependent potentials. Some of these potentials were probed in an earlier generation of the current Hg-Cs co-magnetometer apparatus at Amherst looking for spin-mass couplings [25], as well as other experiments [26, 27]. More generally, as the axion is a possible candidate for cold dark matter (CDM), much effort has been devoted to search for it in both laboratory and astrophysical experiments [28].

1.2.2 Spin-Spin Interactions from Vector Bosons

The success of the Standard Model was partially due to the discoveries of the vector bosons for the weak and strong interactions that it posited. In 2006, Dobrescu and Mocioiu published a paper [29] with calculations on all the possible spin-spin interactions that may happen as a result of the virtual exchange of *any* vector boson, resulting in the potentials

$$V_1 = \frac{g_A^1 g_A^2}{4\pi r} (\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_1 \cdot \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_2) e^{-r/\lambda}, \quad (1.4)$$

$$V_2 = \frac{\hbar^2}{4\pi} \left(\frac{g_V^1 g_A^2}{2M_1} + \frac{g_A^1 g_V^2}{2M_2} \right) (\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_1 \times \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_2) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}} \left(1 + \frac{r}{\lambda} \right) \times \left(\frac{1}{r^2} \right) e^{-r/\lambda} \quad (1.5)$$

$$V_3 = \frac{g_V^1 g_V^2}{16\pi M_1 M_2} \left[(\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_1 \cdot \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_2) \left(\frac{1}{\lambda r^2} + \frac{1}{r^3} + \frac{4\pi}{3} \delta^3(r) \right) - (\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_1 \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}})(\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_2 \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}}) \left(\frac{1}{r\lambda^2} + \frac{3}{r^2\lambda} + \frac{3}{r^3} \right) \right] e^{-r/\lambda}, \quad (1.6)$$

$$V_{6,7} = \frac{\hbar}{8\pi c^2} \left(\frac{g_V^1 g_A^2}{2M_1} + \frac{g_A^1 g_V^2}{2M_2} \right) \times [(\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_1 \cdot \mathbf{v})(\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_2 \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}}) \pm (\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_1 \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}})(\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_2 \cdot \mathbf{v})] \times \left(1 + \frac{r}{\lambda} \right) \frac{e^{-r/\lambda}}{r^2}, \quad (1.7)$$

$$V_8 = \frac{g_A^1 g_A^2}{4\pi c^2} [(\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_1 \cdot \mathbf{v})(\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_2 \cdot \mathbf{v})] \frac{e^{-r/\lambda}}{r}, \quad (1.8)$$

$$V_{14} = \frac{g_A^1 g_A^2}{4\pi c^2} [(\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_1 \times \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_2) \cdot \mathbf{v}] \frac{e^{-r/\lambda}}{r}, \quad (1.9)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
V_{15} = & -\frac{g_V^1 g_V^2 \hbar^2}{8\pi c^3 M_1 M_2} \times [(\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_1 \cdot (\mathbf{v} \times \hat{\mathbf{r}}))(\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_2 \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}}) + (\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_1 \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}})(\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_2 \cdot (\mathbf{v} \times \hat{\mathbf{r}}))] \\
& \times \left(3 + \frac{3r}{\lambda} + \frac{r^2}{\lambda^2}\right) \frac{e^{-r/\lambda}}{r^3}, \tag{1.10}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
V_{16} = & -\frac{\hbar}{8\pi c^2} \left(\frac{g_V^1 g_A^2}{2M_1} + \frac{g_A^1 g_V^2}{2M_2}\right) \\
& \times [(\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_1 \cdot (\mathbf{v} \times \hat{\mathbf{r}}))(\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_2 \cdot \mathbf{v}) + (\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_1 \cdot \mathbf{v})(\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_2 \cdot (\mathbf{v} \times \hat{\mathbf{r}}))] \\
& \times \left(1 + \frac{r}{\lambda}\right) \frac{e^{-r/\lambda}}{r^2}, \tag{1.11}
\end{aligned}$$

where g denotes the vector (V) or axial²(A) coupling constants of fermions 1 or 2,

M is the mass of the fermion, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ is its spin direction, and

$\lambda = \frac{\hbar}{m_{z'} c}$ characterizes the interaction range of the force, where \hbar is Planck's constant divided by 2π and c is the speed of light. We have also used the numbering convention in the original paper and in [2]. Not all of the potentials in the paper are listed here (thus explaining why some numbers such as V_4 do not appear), as not all of them are the spin-spin potentials we are concerned with.

The first potentials up to V_8 are parity even, in that they do not change sign under a parity transformation. Note how V_3 is similar to the potential we described at the very beginning of the chapter (Eq. 1.1); it is indeed called the dipole-dipole potential. In V_1 to V_3 , the power of r in the denominator indicates the range of the interaction. V_3 decays with a factor of $1/r^3$, giving

²An axial vector, also known as a pseudovector, is a quantity that transform like a vector under proper rotation but flips signs under an improper rotation (any transformation that involves a reflection in addition to a proper rotation). The cross product of two “normal” (or polar) vectors is an axial vector. Magnetic fields \mathbf{B} are axial vectors [3].

a relatively short-ranged force compared to V_1 and V_2 . This is important to note as our experiment is mainly sensitive to long-range spin-spin interactions. Note that V_8 to V_{16} are velocity dependent potentials.

As our experiment has sensitivity towards the presence of spin-spin interactions, with the help of a special method involving some geophysics and calculations that will be detailed in section 1.4, it is possible to improve the current bounds on these interactions.

1.3 What LRSSIs are Useful For

The spin-spin potentials discussed in Section 1.2 are general enough such that our experiment is capable of probing any theory that proposes the existence of any new vector gauge bosons. Such particles are sometimes termed Z' bosons, to differentiate them from their Standard Model cousins.

1.3.1 Dark Photons and Massless Gauge Bosons

Some theorists have proposed the existence of gauge bosons that interact with electrically charged particles through a phenomenon known as “kinetic mixing” with the photon, often called “dark” photons as this coupling to ordinary matter is very weak. The hypothesis of “hidden” or “dark” sectors of a rich array of undiscovered particles not interacting with ordinary matter is commonly found in various formulations of string theory. Different theories predict masses for this hypothetical dark photon anywhere from several MeV or GeV to sub-eV levels. There are even theories that propose gauge bosons that kinetically

mix with other Standard Model gauge bosons such as the Z boson that mediates the electroweak force, giving us “dark” Z' bosons [30]. Consequences of the coupling of dark Z' bosons to ordinary matter include exotic atomic parity violations and new decay channels for the Higgs boson [31]. Many experiments have already or are being carried out to probe for dark particles at various mass scales, such as the electron beam dump experiments at the Stanford Linear Accelerator Center (SLAC) [32], the High Energy Accelerator Research Organization in Japan (KEK), and the Laboratoire de l’accelerateur lineaire (LAL) in Orsay, France [33]. In electron beam dump experiments like these, a very intense beam of electrons is directed at a fixed target in order to probe the extremely weak interactions between dark photons and ordinary matter. However, no evidence for them has been found yet.

The question of the existence of completely massless gauge bosons has also been explored. Again, kinetic mixing occurs and allows some very weak interactions with Standard Model fermions. Their presence would affect phenomena like muon and Higgs boson decay, Big Bang nucleosynthesis (the formation of atomic nuclei during the Big Bang), and star cooling. They are also considered a possible dark matter candidate [34].

1.3.2 Unparticles

Another theory we will mention is Georgi’s conjecture of the unparticle [35], which is unlike any other hypothetical particle we have discussed so far. The unparticle is a scale invariant particle that has a non-zero mass, meaning that it can vary its mass, unlike all the other Standard Model particles except

the photon (which has zero mass). Although its mass is undefined, they can still be described by an energy scale Λ , scaling dimension d and dimensionless coupling constant c_A . It turns out that the exchange of an unparticle results in a spin-spin interaction in the long-range limit [36], namely

$$V_u = -c_A^2 \frac{4\sqrt{\pi}\Gamma(d+1/2)\Gamma(2(d-1))}{(2\pi)^{2d}\Gamma(d-1)\Gamma(2d)} (\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_1 \cdot \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_2) \times \left(\frac{\hbar c}{r}\right) \left(\frac{\hbar c}{\Lambda r}\right)^{2d-2}, \quad (1.12)$$

where Γ is the gamma function. Thus our experiment is also capable of probing for the existence of the unparticle with certain values of d .

1.3.3 Other Proposals

LRSSIs are also relevant in probing for torsion gravity, a variant of the Einstein-Cartan theory of gravity, which is an alternative theory of gravity to general relativity that relaxes certain assumptions [37]. In general, the search for Z' bosons is a cornerstone of many contemporary research programs in physics, from high-energy experiments at large particle accelerators all the way to low-energy table-top experiments such as ours. Many other theories have proposed Z' bosons at varying energies, such as E_6 Grand Unified Theories [38], Little Higgs models [39], topcolor models [40], Kaluza-Klein theory [41], just to name a few. This abundance of experimental and theoretical efforts clearly indicates that the hunt for Z' bosons is considered one of the most promising paths for encountering new physics.

1.4 Geophysical Methods to Constrain LRSSIs

In this section, we shall discuss the method by which we extrapolate the results from our apparatus (as well as other relevant experiments) to bounds on exotic spin-spin interactions. This method was first described in our two earlier papers [1, 2].

1.4.1 Basic Concept

There are three ingredients needed to investigate spin-spin interactions (especially ones that are very weak, as we have seen in Section 1.2): first is a large amount of spin-polarized particles that serves as the source of the interaction - the more the better as the interaction will be stronger and more visible. Secondly, one needs a relatively smaller spin-polarized source of particles that can be monitored in the lab, serving as the “test charge” affected by the main source. Finally, one needs a way to modify the extent of the spin-spin interaction, as otherwise we would be stuck with a measurement value that contains the spin-spin interaction signal plus the value of any other physical processes we apply to the apparatus (such as a magnetic field in our case), and be unable to separate these two components. By changing the extent of the spin-spin interaction while keeping these background effects constant, we can subtract the values measured from the two settings to isolate the spin-spin interaction signal. In practice, this modification is done by changing the polarization of the main source or the lab apparatus.

For the main spin source, many previous experiments have used a local

source consisting of a mass of spin-polarized particles placed a short distance from the test apparatus. For example, an experiment at the University of Washington investigating $e^- - e^-$ (electron-electron) couplings used four rings each consisting of Alnico and SmCo magnets positioned inside their torsion balance apparatus [42]. Another experiment at Princeton University investigated $n - n$ (neutron-neutron) couplings using a source of spin-polarized ${}^3\text{He}$ atoms placed 50 cm from their co-magnetometer apparatus [43]. An advantage of such local sources is that it is easy to reverse the polarization, and the short distance between the source and the test apparatus also allows probing of shorter-ranged forces. However, the number of electrons in a local laboratory source is limited to $\sim 10^{22}$ neutrons or $\sim 10^{25}$ electrons due to practical constraints.

In our method, we use the spin-polarized electrons inside the Earth as our source, thinking of them as interacting with the spins in the co-magnetometer in our lab. There are $\sim 10^{49}$ unpaired electrons inside the Earth, and $\sim 10^{42}$ are spin-polarized. This is 17 orders of magnitude more than a typical laboratory source. A trade-off is that these particles are located several thousand of kilometers away, as opposed to tens of centimeters - a difference of 7 orders of magnitude. This makes our method primarily sensitive to interactions that fall off over $1/r^n$ with $n \leq 2$, because with $n = 3$, we lose 21 orders of magnitude, losing our numerical advantage. This is why this thesis is primarily concerned with *long-ranged* (or low mass) spin-spin interactions, and we are not very sensitive to V_3 which has $n = 3$. All of the other potentials in Eqs. 1.4-1.11 have $n = 1$ or 2 with the exception of V_{15} , which has never been experimentally

bounded before. As the spin-polarization of the Earth’s electrons depends on the Earth’s magnetic field, the geographical location of the experiments will be significant, depending on the functional form of the potential we are bounding. Additionally, an important consequence of using the Earth as a spin source is that due to the Earth’s rotation, electrons at different depths will have different velocities relative to each other, and also to our apparatus at the surface. This makes it possible for us to probe for velocity-dependent interactions, something difficult to do with local laboratory spin sources.

A disadvantage of Earth spin sources, however, is that it is not possible to change its polarization. Nevertheless, it is possible to change the orientation of the detector instead, which gives the same effect. Hence experiments which collect data in two different measuring positions (for example by mounting the apparatus on a rotating table), such as in [44–46] as well as our own apparatus [47] can be analyzed with our method.

1.4.2 Taking Experimental Bounds

In our two published papers that utilize our geophysical method, we mainly used the results of three experiments: the first one is our own apparatus, an ^{199}Hg -Cs co-magnetometer located at Amherst, MA ($\theta_{\text{lat}} = 42.37^\circ N, 72.53^\circ W$) [47], the second experiment is located in Seattle, WA ($\theta_{\text{lat}} = 47.66^\circ N, 122.3^\circ W$) [46] and the third one is an earlier experiment also performed in Seattle [48] by the same group. The first two are experiments originally designed to search for Local Lorentz Invariance (LLI) violations, while the third one was looking for couplings between nuclear spin and the Earth’s gravitational field. All

returned null results, and thus can be used to constrain LRSSIs.

In the case of our Amherst experiment (which will be the main subject of the rest of this thesis), the nuclear precession frequency of ^{199}Hg is measured in two table positions separated by 180° , where the horizontal component of the applied magnetic field is pointing towards the North and South geographic poles respectively from our location at Amherst. This alters the direction of the applied magnetic field (\mathbf{B}_{app1} and \mathbf{B}_{app2} in Fig. 1.1). As we will discuss more fully in Chapter 2, this is relevant to measuring spin-spin interactions because spin couples to magnetic fields, so by changing the direction of the applied B -field, we are effectively changing the direction of the spin polarization, giving us the modulation we need to isolate the spin-spin interaction signal.

The latest measurement from our experiment gives the change of the precession frequency between the two table positions to be $\Delta v_N^{\text{Hg}} < 1.1 \mu\text{Hz}$ (with 2σ significance). Taking into account the angle of magnetic field to the vertical ($\theta_B = 63.8^\circ$), this converts to an energy bound of

$$\hat{\beta}_N^{\text{Hg}} < \frac{h\Delta v_N^{\text{Hg}}}{4 \sin \theta_B} = 1.3 \times 10^{-21} \text{ eV}. \quad (1.13)$$

Assuming we know the density of spin-polarized electrons inside the Earth (an arbitrary one is indicated by $\hat{\sigma}_2$), then we can bound the LRSSI potentials delineated in Eqs. 1.4-1.11 by summing the contribution of all of these polarized electrons, taking into account their orientation and position. The resulting combined energy should not exceed $\hat{\beta}_N^{\text{Hg}}$, which will result in bounds for the various coupling constants for the potentials. As we are observing

nuclear precession frequency, our experimental results can be used to bound neutron-electron ($n-e^-$) and proton-electron ($p-e^-$) spin couplings. We have

Figure 1.1: Diagram depicting the location and positions of the Amherst co-magnetometer experiment. Taken from [1].

also measured data with the two table positions oriented East and West (rotated 90° from the original pair of positions), as this was found to give better bounds on some potentials, such as the spin-cross-spin potential of Eq. 1.5. This gave us energy bounds of

$$\hat{\beta}_E^{\text{Hg}} < 9 \times 10^{-22} \text{ eV}. \quad (1.14)$$

The two other Seattle experiments similarly have two different probing positions that result in energy bounds. The newer Seattle experiment gives bounds on electron (e^-) couplings in the North-South and East-West directions

of

$$\hat{\beta}_N < 5.9 \times 10^{-21} \text{eV}, \quad (1.15)$$

$$\hat{\beta}_E < 8 \times 10^{-22} \text{eV}, \quad (1.16)$$

which can be used to bound $e^- - e^-$ spin couplings. The earlier Seattle experiment investigating gravity-spin couplings had an applied magnetic field parallel to the Earth's spin axis (z), giving energy bounds on neutron and proton couplings

$$\hat{\beta}_z^n < 1.2 \times 10^{-20} \text{eV}, \quad (1.17)$$

$$\hat{\beta}_z^p < 1.8 \times 10^{-20} \text{eV}, \quad (1.18)$$

allowing us to bound $n - e^-$ and $p - e^-$ spin couplings. Besides these three experiments, there are others which in principle are also applicable to our method, such as a torsion balance experiment carried out in Taiwan [44]. However, in the final calculation we found that these three experiments give the smallest bounds on the potentials.

1.4.3 Geophysical Model

To use the Earth as a spin source, we must create a fairly accurate geophysical model that profiles the density of spin-polarized electrons inside the Earth according to their location and depth. Thus we must find out the material composition, direction and magnitude of its magnetic field and temperature

profile everywhere inside the Earth, as these all influence the density of spin-polarized electrons. The profile of Earth’s magnetic field is readily available using the World Magnetic Model [49], while the temperature profile of the Earth’s mantle is also widely understood among geophysicists [50]. Finding out the proportions of different minerals and metals at different depths is not as straightforward, however, and the details of our model are given in [1]. Our model ignores the possibility of spin-polarized electrons located inside the Earth’s core, density functional theories indicate that there are no unpaired electron spins in the core due to the high temperatures and pressures [51]. This is a conservative assumption as this will only weaken the bounds obtained from the model. The result of our model is a spin-density map of the entire Earth, a cross-section of which is shown in Fig. 1.2.

1.4.4 Calculating the Bounds

To obtain the actual bounds, we fit the data in our model to find the following three functions:

$\mathbf{B}(r', \theta', \phi')$, the Earth’s magnetic field,

$T(r')$, the temperature of the Earth, and

$\rho(r')$, the electron density,

where r' , θ' , and ϕ' are parameters of a spherical coordinates system with an origin at the center of the Earth’s core. We then calculate V_{total} , the sum of contributions by all of the geoelectrons to the potential, by performing a 3-dimensional integral over the Earth’s volume from the core-mantle boundary

Figure 1.2: A cross-section from the spin-polarized electron density plot we obtained from our geophysical model. Taken from [1].

(R_{CM}) to the surface (R_S), namely

$$V_{\text{total}} = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\pi \int_{R_{CM}}^{R_S} r'^2 \sin \theta' \times \rho(r') \times \frac{2\mu_B \mathbf{B}(r', \theta', \phi')}{k_B T(r')} \\ \times V(\mathbf{r}(r', \theta', \phi'), \mathbf{v}(r', \theta', \phi')) dr' d\theta' d\phi', \quad (1.19)$$

where μ_B is the Bohr magneton,

k_B is Boltzmann's constant, and

$V(\mathbf{r}(r', \theta', \phi')\mathbf{v}(r', \theta', \phi'))$ is the function of the potential being bounded (taken from Eqs. 1.4-1.11), with

$$\mathbf{r}(r', \theta', \phi') = \mathbf{r}'_A - \mathbf{r}', \quad (1.20)$$

where \mathbf{r}'_A is the vector designating the location of Amherst or Seattle, and \mathbf{r}' is the vector designating the location of the geoelectron. For velocity-dependent potentials (Eqs. 1.7-1.11), we also need to calculate the velocity function

$$\mathbf{v}(r', \theta', \phi') = \mathbf{v}'_A - \mathbf{v}', \quad (1.21)$$

with

$$\mathbf{v}'_A = \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r}'_A, \quad (1.22)$$

$$\mathbf{v}' = \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r}', \quad (1.23)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\Omega} = \frac{2\pi}{t_{\text{day}}} \hat{\mathbf{z}}, \quad (1.24)$$

where t_{day} is the length of time of a sidereal day and $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$ is the vector parallel to the rotation axis of the Earth. For non-velocity-dependent potentials then we would only have $V(\mathbf{r}(r', \theta', \phi'))$ in Eq. 1.19. These integrals are numerically calculated using Mathematica for different ranges λ (or different boson masses $m_{Z'}$, since $\lambda \propto 1/m_{Z'}$). To ensure the veracity of such a complicated integral, we perform the calculation using two slightly different methods: in the first, we numerically integrate thin shells of tens of km thickness and manually add them together, while in the second method we instruct Mathematica to directly calculate the full integral. We further ensured the robustness of our bounds by repeating the calculations with double the density of electrons in the lower mantle and taking the worse bound, to take into account any changes in the electron density (or alternatively, disagreements between geologists about our electron density profile).

Fig. 1.3 is an example plot of our bounds, in this case for V_1 . In our two previous papers, the bounds we established on all of the investigated potentials were at least 1-2 orders of magnitude better than previous experimental methods. In the case of velocity-dependent potentials, none of them had been bounded before, with the exception of V_8 , which we improved in the long-range limit by 30 orders of magnitude compared to the previous bound [52].

1.5 Improving the Results

The next step in our research is naturally to improve the bounds calculated using our geophysical method. A conceptually simple way to do this would be

Figure 1.3: Bounds on V_1 for different couplings (electron-electron, electron-proton, and electron-neutron). All regions above the lines are excluded. The violet straight $n-n$ bound near the top is the bound established by a different experimental method in [43]. The full results for all potentials are available in [1] and [2].

to shift the geographic location of our experiment where the Earth's surface magnetic field is stronger and more parallel to the surface. We estimated in [1] that our experiment would be twice as sensitive to LRSSIs were it conducted in a region near the equator (such as southern Thailand). A more practical suggestion, however, would be to improve the apparatus itself. As we will discuss in Ch. 2, the Amherst experiment was limited by AC light shift. We hope to overcome this by implementing a new optical geometry that hopefully will give at least an order of magnitude improvement on our bounds. Besides this, we also anticipate results from other co-magnetometer experiments [53, 54] that will hopefully produce improved energy bounds on spin-couplings to various fermions that can be applied to our model, resulting in improvements in bounds for LRSSIs.

1.6 Summary

To summarize this chapter, we have explored how the search for spin-spin interactions is a natural development of the general quest undertaken by physicists to understand all the different interactions between matter in nature. We have described the specific spin-spin interaction potentials that we are looking for and shown how our new geophysical method is able to transform bounds from several different spin-sensitive experiments into bounds for these LRSSIs. In the following chapters, we shall turn to the more specific case of our own apparatus at Amherst College and discuss our efforts to continue the search for LRSSIs by improving the experiment.

Chapter 2

Physics of the Experiment

In this chapter, we shall discuss the physics of the experimental apparatus in the Hunter Lab at Amherst College. Some basic facts have already been mentioned in Chapter 1: the apparatus is a co-magnetometer, or in other words, a device capable of measuring a magnetic field, and it uses two different types of gas cells to perform this task (hence the “co”): mercury (Hg) and cesium (Cs). Since we have not yet worked with the Hg cells, most of the discussion in this chapter will be focused on Cs. However, most of the physics of optical pumping and probing also applies to Hg. The main differences are the lifetime, precession frequency, and the frequency of the light needed. These differences are all associated with mercury’s different atomic structure. We will delve deeper into the physics of how our magnetometers work, both of the past generation as well as the planned future generation of the experiment. This will allow us to explain why we believe the proposed changes will improve the experiment’s sensitivity.

We shall henceforth refer to the past generation of the apparatus as the *Gen I* magnetometer, while the newly proposed apparatus will be referred to as the *Gen II* magnetometer. We shall constantly note any relevant differences between Gen I and Gen II, in order to gain a comprehensive picture of how the latter should be a definite improvement on the former.

2.1 Basic Concept

Spin is an intrinsic property of particles in nature. It is a particle's inherent angular momentum, and as an intrinsic property it cannot be altered or taken away, similar to mass and charge [55]. Spin is not a classical property like orbital angular momentum, and despite having both magnitude and direction, in quantum mechanics a spin state is not represented by an ordinary vector, but instead by a mathematical object called a *spinor*. Still, in some contexts such as ours a classical picture may remain useful, for example in representing spin by a pseudovector \mathbf{S} . If we are only talking about the direction of the spin, we can also represent it using the vector $\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$, where

$$\mathbf{S}_z = m_z \hbar \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}, \quad (2.1)$$

where m_z is the spin quantum number along a particular axis of quantization (z -axis in this case). When we talk about *spin-polarized* particles, we simply mean that a large number of particles have their spins $\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_i$ oriented along a certain direction of polarization, resulting in a net polarization.

In order to be able to detect spin-spin interactions in a way that is useful

for the geophysical method explained in Chapter 1, one needs to be able to create a source of spin-polarized particles in the lab, and also keep track of the spins. To accomplish the latter, in this experiment we take advantage of the fact that spin couples to magnetic fields, as expressed in the Hamiltonian

$$H = -\boldsymbol{\mu} \cdot \mathbf{B}_{\text{app}} = -\gamma \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{B}_{\text{app}}, \quad (2.2)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ is the magnetic dipole moment, \mathbf{B}_{app} is an applied magnetic field, γ is the gyromagnetic ratio of the particle and \mathbf{S} represents the spin of the particle. If exotic spin-spin interactions exist, then such interactions would be added on to the Hamiltonian:

$$H' = -\gamma \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{B}_{\text{app}} + V(\mathbf{S}), \quad (2.3)$$

where $V(\mathbf{S})$ is a potential (such as one of those defined in Eq. 1.4-1.11) which depends on the spin \mathbf{S} of the particle. As both terms in H' contain \mathbf{S} , we can rework the equation by pulling out \mathbf{S} . The details would depend on the actual form of $V(\mathbf{S})$. For example, let us take the potential V_1 , defined previously in Eq. 1.4 as taking the form of

$$V_1 = K(\mathbf{S}_L \cdot \mathbf{S}_E), \quad (2.4)$$

where K is a variable containing variables r and λ and also other constants as needed, and we use the notation \mathbf{S}_L for a spin in the lab and \mathbf{S}_E for a spin inside the Earth. Note that we have converted the $\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ spin vectors appearing

in the original Eq. 1.4 into \mathbf{S} . Then Eq. 2.3 becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
H' &= -\gamma \mathbf{S}_L \cdot \mathbf{B}_{\text{app}} + K(\mathbf{S}_L \cdot \mathbf{S}_E) \\
&= -\gamma \mathbf{S}_L \cdot \left(\mathbf{B}_{\text{app}} - \frac{K}{\gamma} \mathbf{S}_E \right) \\
&= \boldsymbol{\mu} \cdot \mathbf{B}_{\text{eff}}.
\end{aligned} \tag{2.5}$$

So if V_1 exists, then it would have the effect of altering the magnetic field experienced by the particle. Similar manipulation can be done to the other potentials to arrive at the same conclusion. Thus we can search for LRSSIs by subjecting the particle to a fixed magnetic field \mathbf{B}_{app} and pointing our apparatus to different directions in order to look for any changes in the magnetic field which may be caused by any of these exotic interactions. It is essential that one is able to change the direction of \mathbf{B}_{app} in order to modulate the spin-spin interaction signal. Otherwise we would be stuck with a certain value of the measured effective magnetic field and not know how much of it is due to \mathbf{B}_{app} and how much of it is due to LRSSIs.

To monitor the magnetic field, we observe the *Larmor frequency* of the particle, which is the natural frequency at which the magnetic moment $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ precesses in the magnetic field \mathbf{B}_{app} , as seen in Fig. 2.1. This precession is caused by a torque

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \boldsymbol{\mu} \times \mathbf{B}_{\text{app}}, \tag{2.6}$$

which in the figure points out of the page.

Figure 2.1: Precession of a magnetic moment $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ about a magnetic field, which is here directed along the z -axis.

The Larmor angular frequency ω itself¹ is given by the equation [56]

$$\boldsymbol{\omega} = \mathbf{B}_{\text{app}}\gamma, \quad (2.7)$$

and so with the effect of spin-spin interactions as described in Eq. 2.5, the altered frequency will be

$$\boldsymbol{\omega}' = \left(\mathbf{B}_{\text{app}} - \frac{K}{\gamma} \mathbf{S}_E \right) \gamma. \quad (2.8)$$

In our co-magnetometer, we make use of the Larmor frequency of two different kinds of atoms, ^{199}Hg and ^{133}Cs . In the plan for the Gen II apparatus, there are two Cs cells and one Hg cell, all immersed a homogeneous magnetic field \mathbf{B}_{app} using a pair of Helmholtz coils. (Note that we have chosen our z -axis to be along this B -field direction.) They are stacked on top of each with the Hg cell sandwiched between the two Cs cells (Fig. 2.2), and the precession

¹The angular frequency ω is related to the rotation frequency ν by the equation $\omega = 2\pi\nu$.

frequencies of the three cells are monitored independently.

Figure 2.2: Three-cell stack of Hg and Cs in co-magnetometer.

The magnetic field and its gradient will be locked to the average of the frequencies of the two Cs cells, meaning that continuous adjustments are made to ensure that they do not change. This is done using several pairs of Helmholtz and anti-Helmholtz coils. The anti-Helmholtz pair allows to control dBz/dz , the B -field gradient along the z -axis, which together with other pairs of Helmholtz coils (oriented in all three dimensions) allow full control of the B -field. Thus we hold the magnetic field at the Hg cell approximately constant, reducing drift. At the same time, we will also monitor the precession frequency of the Hg cell, looking for any changes as we point \mathbf{B}_{app} in different directions via the use of the rotating table. As we have ensured that the Cs frequency stays constant, any changes to the Hg frequency will allow us to identify the difference of how the spins couple to Hg as compared to Cs.

The presence of two different atoms enables us to decrease magnetic noise, as shown by the argument in Chapter 1 of David Stein's thesis [56], which I will partially recap and adapt here. Let us first assume that we are looking for interactions in the form of potential V_1 . Then following Eq. 2.8 but adding the

presence of magnetic field noise $\mathbf{B}_{\text{noise}}$, the precession frequency of the cesium atoms ω_{Cs} is given by

$$\omega_{Cs} = \gamma_{Cs} \left(\mathbf{B}_{\text{app}} + \mathbf{B}_{\text{noise}} - \frac{K_{Cs}}{\gamma_{Cs}} \mathbf{S}_E \right). \quad (2.9)$$

In order to counteract $\mathbf{B}_{\text{noise}}$, we adjust the applied magnetic field such that

$$\mathbf{B}'_{\text{app}} = \frac{\omega_{Cs}}{\gamma_{Cs}} - \mathbf{B}_{\text{noise}} + \frac{K_{Cs}}{\gamma_{Cs}} \mathbf{S}_E. \quad (2.10)$$

Similarly, the precession frequency of the mercury atoms ω_{Hg} is given by

$$\omega_{Hg} = \gamma_{Hg} \left(\mathbf{B}'_{\text{app}} + \mathbf{B}_{\text{noise}} - \frac{K_{Hg}}{\gamma_{Hg}} \mathbf{S}_E \right). \quad (2.11)$$

But if we plug in \mathbf{B}'_{app} from Eq. 2.10, this will result in cancellation of $\mathbf{B}_{\text{noise}}$, giving us

$$\omega_{Hg} = \gamma_{Hg} \left[\frac{\omega_{Cs}}{\gamma_{Cs}} + \left(\frac{K_{Cs}}{\gamma_{Cs}} - \frac{K_{Hg}}{\gamma_{Hg}} \right) \mathbf{S}_E \right]. \quad (2.12)$$

If we calculate the magnitude of ω_{Hg} , and make the approximation $\hat{\omega}_{Hg} \approx \hat{\mathbf{B}}'_{\text{app}}$, we will obtain

$$\omega_{Hg} = |\omega_{Hg}| = \frac{\gamma_{Hg}}{\gamma_{Cs}} \omega_{Cs} + \gamma_{Hg} (\mathbf{B}'_{\text{app}} \cdot \mathbf{S}_E) \left(\frac{K_{Cs}}{\gamma_{Cs}} - \frac{K_{Hg}}{\gamma_{Hg}} \right). \quad (2.13)$$

Thus by pointing \mathbf{B}'_{app} in different directions and looking for changes in ω_{Hg} , we will be able to learn something about the spin-spin interaction second term in Eq. 2.13.

2.2 Optical Pumping

How does one look for changes in the precession frequencies ω_{Hg} and ω_{Cs} ? While all of the atoms are precessing together in the constant applied magnetic field, they are all out of phase with each other, and thus we cannot probe the entire system. Our first step is to make all the atoms in a cell have a net spin polarization. This is accomplished by *optical pumping*, in which we apply electromagnetic radiation tuned at a certain resonant frequency to the atoms. The resonant light transfers its angular momentum to the atoms. For the case of Cs, we use circularly polarized light from a diode laser tuned to the $6^2S_{1/2} \rightarrow 6^2P_{1/2}$ transition, also known as the D_1 transition. This corresponds to a frequency of about 894 nm, and this transition is used for both the pump and probe lasers. We shall now elaborate further both of the Cs transitions and also the details of how optical pumping works.

2.2.1 The Cs D_1 Transition

Cesium is an alkali metal, i.e., it comes from the first column of the periodic table, and thus has one valence electron. Cesium-133 is its only stable isotope, possessing a total nuclear angular momentum $I = 7/2$. In quantum mechanics, the possible hyperfine quantum numbers F are defined by

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{J} + \mathbf{I} \tag{2.14}$$

where the magnitude of \mathbf{F} can take on the values

$$|J - I| < F < J + I. \quad (2.15)$$

The $6^2S_{1/2} \rightarrow 6^2P_{1/2}$ transition has $J = 1/2$ for both states, and so we can only have $F = 3$ or $F = 4$, resulting in only two hyperfine levels for both the ground and excited states. These two levels are easy to resolve and work with, making this an attractive transition for optical pumping as we have only four energy levels in total. The level diagram is shown in Fig. 2.3. A graph showing the response of Cs atoms to laser light at around 894 nm is shown in Fig. 2.4. This also shows the relative light frequencies needed for each of the four transitions. Note how the $(F = 3) \rightarrow (F' = 4)$ transition has the the highest frequency as we can see in Fig. 2.3. For pumping, we tune and lock our laser to the center of this transition.

Figure 2.3: Hyperfine structure diagram of Cs for the $6^2S_{1/2} \rightarrow 6^2P_{1/2}$ transition. Energy levels are not drawn to scale. Data taken from [57].

These F hyperfine levels are not the whole picture, however. There are magnetic sublevels m_F in each of these hyperfine levels. Without a magnetic

Figure 2.4: Hyperfine response of cesium atoms to laser light, as measured using our probe laser shining through an external reference cell and going to a photodetector. The piezo voltage is proportional to the laser frequency and the laser current is inversely proportional to the laser frequency, which is why the highest frequency transition ($F = 3 \rightarrow F' = 4$) has the highest piezo voltage on the lower current-graph. The upper graph was taken on a higher current setting than the lower graph. Its y -values have been rescaled such that the background is equal to those of the lower graph.

field, the energies of these sublevels are degenerate. However, in the presence of a magnetic field, as in our experiment, the Zeeman effect breaks the degeneracy, giving different energies for the sublevels [57].

2.2.2 A Basic Two-Level System

Figure 2.5: Basic geometry of our experiment, with circularly polarized light (here depicted as σ^+ , left-circularly polarized), and a B -field along the z -axis coming out of the page. At any given point, due to the magnetic field, an atom has its angular momentum \mathbf{s} precessing around the z -axis.

Merely shining constant light at the atoms is not, however, sufficient for our system, as explained by the following argument, adapted from Happer's classic 1972 paper on optical pumping [58] and Stein's thesis [56]. Let us imagine our Cs atoms as being a simple two level system with $6^2S_{1/2}$ and $6^2P_{1/2}$ being the fine structure levels. Next, define a quantization axis y along the direction of propagation of the light (see Fig. 2.5). At any given time, an atom has a certain angular momentum projection along y . In this system, we only consider the fine structure with total electron angular momentum $J = 1/2$, so the quantum

state can be expressed in the form

$$|\psi\rangle = A|+y\rangle + B|-y\rangle, \quad (2.16)$$

where A and B describe the probability amplitudes for the atom being in the state $m_j = +1/2$ or $m_j = -1/2$ respectively. Let us assume that we are shining left-circularly polarized light (commonly denoted as σ^+). An atom which already has $m_j = +1/2$, i.e. its angular momentum is completely along the direction of $+y$ with $A = 1$, cannot accommodate additional angular momentum, so it cannot absorb photons from the laser light and will remain in the ground state. In contrast, atoms with $m_j = -1/2$ ($B = 1$) can absorb a photon, which will excite it to the state $6^2P_{1/2}$ with $m_j = 1/2$. The majority of atoms will be in some intermediate state

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{2}(1 + e^{i\theta})|+y\rangle + \frac{1}{2}(1 - e^{i\theta})|-y\rangle, \quad (2.17)$$

where θ denotes the angle of its angular momentum from the y -axis (see Fig. 2.5). Thus the probability of absorbing a photon will be

$$P(\text{absorb}) = P_{-y} |\langle -y|\psi\rangle|^2 \quad (2.18)$$

$$= \frac{P_{-y}}{4} (1 + e^{i\theta})(1 + e^{-i\theta}) \quad (2.19)$$

$$= \frac{P_{-y}}{2} (1 + \cos\theta), \quad (2.20)$$

$$= P_{-y} \cos^2 \frac{\theta}{2} \quad (2.21)$$

$$= P_{-y} \cos^2 \frac{\omega t}{2} \quad (2.22)$$

where P_{-y} denotes the probability of absorption when $A = 1$. In the last line, we use the relation $\theta = \omega t$, as the spins precess at the Larmor frequency. To properly calculate P_{-y} , one would have to work out the necessary quantum mechanics using density matrices [58] or rate equations [59], which are beyond the reach of a typical undergraduate curriculum, but for our purposes, it does not matter what value P_{-y} takes as long as it is non-zero. If, say, P_{-y} is a small fraction, then the left-circularly polarized light would still be absorbed by the atom, although it might take a long time before a coherent polarization occurs. The sinusoidal term in Eq. 2.22 creates a modulation in the absorption in the light, which will in turn result in a modulation in the intensity of the transmitted light. But because the system is initially unpolarized, each individual atom has its own values for A and B and they will absorb photons at different times. Also, excited atoms may collide with the walls of the cell and relax back to the ground state. Relaxation to the ground state also occurs through spontaneous emission. In the end, we have a collection of atoms being excited and decaying all at different times, resulting in only a very small net angular momentum polarization along the direction of the pump. This is insufficient for our needs, and so we introduce modulation to our pump light.

2.2.3 Modulated Pump Light: the Bell-Bloom Magnetometer

Optical pumping using modulated pump light was first suggested by Dehmelt and performed by Bell and Bloom in 1957 [60]. To understand how it works,

consider again Fig. 2.5.² The Cs cell is immersed in a uniform magnetic field $\mathbf{B} = B_0\hat{\mathbf{z}}$, and left-circularly polarized pump light σ^+ is directed along the y -axis. The light is amplitude-modulated (using square waves) at a frequency ω_m , while the Larmor frequency of the Cs is ω_{Cs} as before. Now assume that $\omega_m = \omega_{Cs}$, and at time $t = t_0$ light strikes the cell.³ Some atoms will have a quantum state with $A = 1$ (from Eq. 2.16), and so they are already spin-polarized in the direction we want. All the other atoms, which have $0 \leq A < 1$, have some probability of getting pumped to the excited state. At $t = t_0 + 2\pi/\omega_{Cs}$, light will strike the cell again. Atoms which had been excited at $t = t_0$ will now have $A = 1$, and cannot be affected by the light. But all the other atoms, including those which did not get excited, will now “get a second chance” to be excited, so to speak, and some will indeed end up being excited, adding to the total spin polarization of the system. At the same time the polarization obtained at $t = t_0$ remains. The same process continues at $t = t_0 + 4\pi/\omega_{Cs}$, $t = t_0 + 6\pi/\omega_{Cs}$, and so on. Assuming no other depolarizing forces are present, eventually all of the atoms will be precessing together in phase with the same polarization. In reality, the polarization will increase until a certain value where the rate of pumping is equal to the rate of the depolarization.

If the pumping laser is turned off, then the atoms’ spins will keep precessing together for a while, but with a decay constant of T_2 , which we call the *lifetime* of the cell. T_2 is affected by several factors, such as the design of the cell,

²The following explanation is inspired by Chapter 1 of Budker and Kimball’s book on optical magnetometry [61].

³For simplicity, let us assume that all of the photons in a single oscillation of the pump light are absorbed in an instant instead of over some non-zero amount of time.

whether an anti-relaxation coating is used for the cell walls, and also atoms colliding with each other and causing spin exchange which de-excites them. The longer T_2 is, the more time we have to observe the cell before the spin polarization disappears.

Atoms which are de-excited may decay from the $6^2P_{1/2}(F' = 3)$ state to either the $6^2S_{1/2}(F = 3)$ or $6^2S_{1/2}(F = 4)$ state. As we only pump using a single laser at the $F = 3 \rightarrow F' = 4$ transition, the $6^2S_{1/2}(F = 4)$ state is technically a “dark” state, unreachable by our lasers. However, in practice enough natural spin-exchange collisions happen such that many atoms in the dark state decay into the lowest ground state ($6^2S_{1/2}(F = 3)$), such that there is always a sizable fraction of the atoms in this state, allowing us to freely pump and let the atoms decay multiple times.

We can also think about the system as being a driven harmonic oscillator, with the natural frequency $\Omega_n = \omega_{Cs}$ and the driving frequency $\Omega_d = \omega_m$. The largest amplitude of oscillation will occur when $\Omega_n = \Omega_d$. This is also convenient as we can introduce the idea of a damping force, corresponding to the various forces that cause the decay of the spin polarization. In order for the driven harmonic oscillator to achieve a significant amplitude of oscillation, the damping force has to be much smaller than the driving force.

2.3 Optical Probing

In order to monitor the actual precession caused by the optical pumping, we use a separate diode laser which we call the probe laser. Unlike the circularly po-

larized pump laser, the probe laser is linearly polarized and is not modulated, but shining constantly. It is also tuned about 3 GHz off the $F = 4 \rightarrow F' = 3$ transition. The laser light passes through the pumped Cs cells in an orthogonal direction to the pump beam, and picked up by photodetectors on the other side. Optical probing in this manner allows us to observe the precession frequencies of our atoms by a process known as *optical rotation*.

2.3.1 Light Polarization and Optical Rotation

The linearly polarized probe light propagating along the x -axis can be viewed as a superposition of right- and left- circularly polarized light, i.e., [62]

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(E_+(\hat{\mathbf{y}} + i\hat{\mathbf{z}}) + E_-(\hat{\mathbf{y}} - i\hat{\mathbf{z}}))e^{(i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x} - i\omega t)}, \quad (2.23)$$

where the first term represents the left-circularly polarized component with complex amplitude E_+ (for positive helicity) and the second represents the right-circularly polarized component with complex amplitude E_- (negative helicity), and the light is propagating along the x -axis with frequency ω . Since this is linearly polarized light, $|E_+| = |E_-|$. For our linearly polarized light, the relative phase between E_+ and E_- determines the plane of the linear polarization.

In this setup, we can treat optical rotation as the result of the different indices of refraction experienced by the left- and right-circularly polarized components of the probe light. We can apply Eq. 2.22 to the index of refraction of the atomic vapor, with a π phase difference between the two components, as

the absorption of the left-circularly polarized component will be the greatest when the right circularly component is at the smallest, and vice versa. But before we can do this, we have to first derive the formula for the index of refraction.

2.3.2 Deriving the Index of Refraction

In Chapter 9 of [3], Griffiths derives the index of refraction experienced by light traveling through a collection of atoms by modeling each atom as a damped harmonic oscillator with the light as a driving force. We shall quote some of the derivation here. We start with a single electron on a single atom, imagining it as being attached to a spring with force constant k , and the photons of the laser light as subjecting it to an oscillating driving force. To make the mathematics easier, we represent the system as a complex equation:

$$m \frac{d^2 \tilde{x}}{dt^2} = F_{binding} + F_{damping} + F_{driving}, \quad (2.24)$$

$$\implies m \frac{d^2 \tilde{x}}{dt^2} + m\gamma \frac{d\tilde{x}}{dt} + m\omega_0^2 \tilde{x} = qE_0 e^{-i\omega t}, \quad (2.25)$$

where m is the mass of the electron,

γ is a parameter characterizing the damping force,

ω_0 is the oscillation frequency of the system,

q is the charge of the electron,

E_0 is the amplitude of the wave when it hits the electron, and

ω is the frequency of the laser light. The steady state oscillation of the system will be equal to the driving frequency. The displacement of the electron will

follow a function of the form

$$\tilde{x}(t) = \tilde{x}_0 e^{-i\omega t}. \quad (2.26)$$

Plugging this into Eq. 2.25, we get

$$\tilde{x}_0 = \frac{q/m}{\omega_0^2 - \omega^2 - i\gamma\omega} E_0, \quad (2.27)$$

and the dipole moment $\tilde{p}(t)$ can be calculated using the relation

$$\tilde{p}(t) = q\tilde{x}(t). \quad (2.28)$$

We then expand our model so that there are multiple electrons in different places around the atom, each of them acting as a damped harmonic oscillator. Assume that there are j groups of electrons, where each group has f_j electrons and has its own resonant frequencies ω_j and damping coefficient γ_j . Their dipole moments combine to form a complex polarization \mathbf{P} of the medium. Now, the *complex susceptibility* $\tilde{\chi}_e$ of the medium is defined as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{P}} = \epsilon_0 \tilde{\chi}_e \tilde{\mathbf{E}}, \quad (2.29)$$

where ϵ_0 is the permittivity of free space. By summing up all the dipole moments of the different electron groups around the atom, we get

$$\tilde{\mathbf{P}} = \frac{Nq^2}{m} \left(\sum_j \frac{f_j}{\omega_j^2 - \omega^2 - i\gamma_j\omega} \right) \tilde{\mathbf{E}}, \quad (2.30)$$

from which we can extract the value of $\tilde{\chi}_e$.

We then take plane wave solution of the wave equation

$$\tilde{\mathbf{E}}(x, t) = \tilde{\mathbf{E}}_0 e^{i(\tilde{k}x - \omega t)} \quad (2.31)$$

$$= \tilde{\mathbf{E}}_0 e^{i((k+i\xi)x - \omega t)}, \quad (2.32)$$

$$= \tilde{\mathbf{E}}_0 e^{-\xi x} e^{i(kx - \omega t)} \quad (2.33)$$

where we have assumed a beam propagating in the x -direction (as in our apparatus) and broken up complex wave number \tilde{k} into its real and imaginary parts, $\tilde{k} = k + i\xi$. Eq. 2.33 shows that the wave is attenuated, and its intensity will be proportional to $e^{-2\xi x}$. Thus we can define an *absorption coefficient* α by

$$\alpha = 2\xi \quad (2.34)$$

and also calculate the index of refraction n by the formula

$$n = \frac{ck}{\omega}. \quad (2.35)$$

Using the formula for $\tilde{\chi}_e$ and the relation

$$\tilde{k} = \omega \sqrt{\mu_0 \epsilon_0 (1 + \tilde{\chi}_e)} \quad (2.36)$$

and doing some approximations along the way, eventually we will get

$$n = 1 + \frac{Nq^2}{2m\epsilon_0} \sum_j \frac{f_j(\omega_j^2 - \omega^2)}{(\omega_j^2 - \omega^2)^2 + \gamma_j^2 \omega^2}, \quad (2.37)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{Nq^2\omega}{m\epsilon_0c} \sum_j \frac{f_j\gamma_j}{(\omega_j^2 - \omega^2)^2 + \gamma_j^2\omega^2}, \quad (2.38)$$

where N is the number of atoms per volume.

Now that we have derived the index of refraction, we can apply it to our system as we outlined in Sec. 2.3.1. Referring back to the analogy of a photon striking an electron, we must also take into account that in our system, the probability of such an event happening is affected by the probabilities of light absorption expressed in Eq. 2.22. When the polarization is pointing along the $-x$ direction, only the left-circularly polarized component can be absorbed, and when it is along the $+x$ direction, only the right-circularly polarized component can be absorbed. Thus, we have to multiply sinusoidal terms that are π out of phase to the index of refraction experienced by left- and right-circularly polarized components of the probe light, i.e.

$$n_+ = \cos^2\left(\frac{\Omega t}{2}\right) \left(1 + \frac{Nq^2}{2m\epsilon_0} \sum_j \frac{f_j(\omega_j^2 - \omega^2)}{(\omega_j^2 - \omega^2)^2 + \gamma_j^2\omega^2}\right), \quad (2.39)$$

$$\begin{aligned} n_- &= \cos^2\left(\frac{\Omega t + \pi}{2}\right) \left(1 + \frac{Nq^2}{2m\epsilon_0} \sum_j \frac{f_j(\omega_j^2 - \omega^2)}{(\omega_j^2 - \omega^2)^2 + \gamma_j^2\omega^2}\right) \\ &= \sin^2\left(\frac{\Omega t}{2}\right) \left(1 + \frac{Nq^2}{2m\epsilon_0} \sum_j \frac{f_j(\omega_j^2 - \omega^2)}{(\omega_j^2 - \omega^2)^2 + \gamma_j^2\omega^2}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (2.40)$$

This oscillation in the indices of refraction causes the optical rotation.

2.3.3 Implications of the Index of Refraction

We can plot α and n from Eq. 2.38 about a resonant frequency ω_j in order to see how the behavior of the light around the line center of the atomic transition

frequency. We assume that the other resonances are far away, and so only one of the terms in the summation survives. As ω is very close to ω_j , we make the approximation that $\omega_j \approx \omega$, and so $(\omega + \omega_j) \approx 2\omega_j$. Thus we obtain

$$n = 1 + \frac{Nq^2}{2m\epsilon_0} \left(\frac{f_j(\omega_j^2 - \omega^2)}{(\omega_j^2 - \omega^2)^2 + \gamma_j^2\omega^2} \right) \quad (2.41)$$

$$\implies n - 1 \approx \frac{Nq^2}{2m\epsilon_0} \left(\frac{f_j(2\omega_j)^2(\omega_j - \omega)}{(2\omega_j)^2(\omega_j - \omega)^2 + \gamma_j^2\omega^2} \right) \quad (2.42)$$

$$\approx \frac{Nq^2}{m\epsilon_0} \left(\frac{2f_j\Delta\omega}{4(\Delta\omega)^2 + \gamma_j^2} \right) \quad (2.43)$$

and

$$\alpha = \frac{Nq^2}{2m\epsilon_0 c} \left(\frac{\omega f_j \gamma_j}{(\omega_j^2 - \omega^2)^2 + \gamma_j^2\omega^2} \right) \quad (2.44)$$

$$\approx \frac{Nq^2}{2m\epsilon_0 c} \left(\frac{\omega f_j \gamma_j}{(2\omega_j)^2(\omega_j - \omega)^2 + \gamma_j^2\omega^2} \right) \quad (2.45)$$

$$\approx \frac{Nq^2}{2m\epsilon_0 c \omega_j} \left(\frac{f_j \gamma_j}{4(\Delta\omega)^2 + \gamma_j^2} \right), \quad (2.46)$$

where $\Delta\omega = \omega_j - \omega$.

Using Mathematica and setting $f_j = 1$ and $\gamma_j = Nq^2/2m\epsilon_0 = 1$ for simplicity,⁴ we obtain the plots shown in Fig. 2.6. Notice that with increasing $\Delta\omega$, the absorption of the light decays faster than the index of refraction which causes optical rotation. This is the reason why we tune 3 GHz off resonance: to avoid absorption as much as possible (as that will depolarize the atoms) while still observing optical rotation. The different behavior of the real and imaginary parts of the change in index of refraction allows this to work. We

⁴We also disregard the factor of $2/\omega_j c$ in Eq. 2.46, again for simplicity of our plots.

further reduce the depolarization from the probe by setting its peak power to be a factor of 2 weaker than the pump beam.

After going through the atoms, the probe light goes through a beam-splitting cube that separates the light into two orthogonal linearly polarized components that are each sent to a different photodiode. A circuit board takes the differences between the signals of the two photodiodes and sends it to either the computer or the lock-in amplifier, depending on which of the two possible methods of pumping and probing we choose, which shall be discussed later in this chapter.

A full diagram of the Gen II experimental geometry can be seen in Fig. 2.7. The cells and B -field coils are surrounded by three layers of magnetic shielding. The shields protect the experiment from the effects of the Earth field and local magnetic field variations. The quarter wave-plate (QWP) converts the linearly polarized pump beam into circularly polarized light (as will be elaborated upon more fully in Chapter 3).

Figure 2.6: Plots of the index of refraction n and absorption coefficient α , generated using Mathematica. The absolute values on the axes are not meaningful, but we clearly see that with increasing $\Delta\omega$, the absorption decreases more sharply than the refraction, which is advantageous for our experiment.

Figure 2.7: Diagram of new Bell-Bloom magnetometer geometry (Gen II).

2.4 The Old Gen I Experiment

In this section, we will review basic features of the previous generation of our magnetometer apparatus. Much work has been done by several previous students on this experiment dating back to 2002 [63–66]; the most comprehensive document is David Stein’s thesis [56]. Most of the details on the Gen I apparatus have been thoroughly expounded in these theses, and so here we will only recap the features as needed.

2.4.1 Searching for Local Lorentz Invariance

The Gen I optical magnetometer was used to search not for LRSSIs but for violations of Local Lorentz Invariance (LLI). An LLI violation would constitute a coupling between the spin of a particle to a direction in space, in the form of

$$H = K\mathbf{s} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \quad (2.47)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{r}}$ points along the preferred direction and K is a coupling constant. Apart from this, the physics is similar to our current search for LRSSIs; after obtaining the upper limit for the difference in Hg frequency between the two table positions (Δv_N^{Hg}), instead of chugging it through the equations for various LRSSI potentials, we would just use Eq. 2.47. The latest experimental results for this experiment was published in [47]. Gen I was mainly concerned with upper bounds for couplings to directions in the plane of the Earth’s rotation (in other words, equatorial dipole couplings); this is the parameter \tilde{b}_\perp . The apparatus also had sensitivity to directional couplings along the Earth’s spin

axis \tilde{b}_z . While Gen I initially had the best limits on \tilde{b}_\perp , eventually other experiments superseded it for couplings for the neutron and proton [43] as well as the electron [67]. Gen I still had the best limits on \tilde{b}_z , a somewhat less attractive parameter as it only deals with couplings along a single line. With the advent of the new geophysical method detailed in Chapter 1, however, the apparatus has a newfound purpose as it turned out to be better than other experiments for bounding LRSSIs for several regimes. This led to the project of the present thesis.

2.4.2 The M_x -Geometry of Gen I

The optical geometry of Gen I is commonly termed the M_x geometry [61], shown in Fig. 2.8. Unlike Gen II, this geometry uses a single beam to both pump and probe the atoms, which in the figure is depicted as propagating along the z -axis. As we used the same $6^2S_{1/2} \rightarrow 6^2P_{1/2}$ transition for the Cs cells,⁵ the laser was also circularly polarized and tuned to 894.4 nm, but it is shining constantly instead of being modulated. For the Hg cells, ultraviolet 254 nm light was used to pump the $6^1S_0(F = \frac{1}{2}) \rightarrow 6^3P_1(F' = \frac{1}{2})$ transition. A static magnetic field \mathbf{B}_{app} is directed at an angle θ_B from the z -axis. As the lasers are constantly on, while the atoms will still be optically pumped, their spins will not precess in phase. While there is still a net polarization along \mathbf{B} , the transverse polarization will be scrambled so there is no observable precession. This is where the oscillating magnetic field \mathbf{B}_{osc} comes into play, directed along the y -axis. The field is oscillating at the Larmor frequency, and

⁵A small difference was that the hyperfine levels used were $F = 4$ to $F' = 3$.

Figure 2.8: M_x geometry of Gen I magnetometer. Diagram taken from [47].

its net effect will be to cause all the spins to precess in phase together. The full derivation of this is contained in [56], and will not be repeated here.

At the other end of the apparatus, photodetectors are placed to receive the light coming through the vapor cells. Unlike Gen II, which uses optical rotation on linearly polarized light, Gen I simply detects the modulation in the absorption of the circularly polarized light, as seen in Eq. 2.22, which will be sinusoidal once all the atoms are pumped with their spins precessing together. The modulated signals are then processed through lock-in amplifiers. A more detailed explanation of how lock-in amplifiers work will be discussed in Chapter 3. The lock-ins essentially convert the difference between the Larmor precession frequency and the magnetic field modulation frequency into a phase that becomes the monitored signal.

As in the plans for Gen II (Fig. 2.7), the entire apparatus is then fitted

with multiple magnetic shields that attenuate the effect of Earth's magnetic field and mounted on a rotating table that allowed us to vary the direction of \mathbf{B}_{app} (Fig. 2.9).

Figure 2.9: Detailed diagram of Gen I apparatus. Diagram taken from [47].

In each data run, the Cs phase is locked (for the reasons enumerated in Section 2.1), while the phase of the Hg frequency (which is allowed to freely

vary) is monitored for a set amount of time (in this case, 124 seconds) with the apparatus is in one table position. The table is then rotated into the other position, and the phase is monitored for the same period of time. This process was reiterated over about a week, and that constitutes one full data run.

A total of 12 data runs were needed to result in the bounds published in [47]. As the data was collected over multiple days, the apparatus did indeed detect frequency shifts between the table positions, an average value of $\Delta\nu_{\text{offset}} = 15.75(5) \mu\text{Hz}$.

Most of this difference was due to the rotation frequency of the Earth, which at a period of 23 hours, 56 minutes, and 4 seconds is $11.6 \mu\text{Hz}$. From a combination of several factors such as the ratio of the gyromagnetic ratios of Hg and Cs, a misalignment between the apparatus and true north, and also a small effect by the Earth's gyroscopic motion on the Cs oscillator, the apparatus was calculated to have a sensitivity to the Earth's gyroscopic frequency $\nu_{\text{pred}} = 15.39(2) \mu\text{Hz}$. Thus there remained a difference of $\Delta\nu_g = 0.36(7) \mu\text{Hz}$, which was thought probably not to have come as a result of LLI violations nor LRSSIs but a systematic limitation of the Gen I apparatus, namely *AC light shift*. This will be the subject of the next section.

2.5 AC Light Shift

Light shifts are shifts in the atomic energy levels that occur due to laser light. Mathur et. al [68] identify the general light shift operator δE as consisting of

four terms:⁶

$$\delta E = \delta E_0 + h\delta A \mathbf{I} \cdot \mathbf{J} - \boldsymbol{\mu} \cdot \delta \mathbf{H} + \delta E_2. \quad (2.48)$$

The first term δE_0 is called the *center of mass light shift*, and results in equal displacement of all energy levels. As in optical pumping we are only concerned about the differences between energy levels, it is not relevant to our experiment. The second term, $h\delta A \mathbf{I} \cdot \mathbf{J}$, is called the *hyperfine structure light shift* and depends on the spectral profile of the light but not its polarization. It does affect transitions with $\Delta F = 1$, but it does not affect the magnetic sub-levels m_F . The third term, $\boldsymbol{\mu} \cdot \delta \mathbf{H}$, is a *Zeeman light shift* which occurs when the light has some circular polarization, and it is the main form of light shift that we are concerned about, and which we have been referring to as *AC light shift* due to it arising from circularly polarized light. As stated in Mathur's paper, this light shift can be thought of as an additional magnetic field \mathbf{H} pointing parallel or anti-parallel to the direction of propagation of the light and interacting with the atom to cause additional Zeeman shifts.

2.5.1 AC Light Shift in Gen I

In Gen I, the applied B -field (\mathbf{B}_{app} in Fig. 2.8) was at an angle $\theta_B = 63.8^\circ$ from the propagation direction of the circularly polarized light beam. Thus a significant component of the virtual B -field arising from the Zeeman light shift affected the magnetic field experienced by the atoms. This can be seen

⁶The use of δ in front of each of these terms is a convention initially adapted by Happer and Mathur in their 1961 paper about operator formalism in discussions of optical pumping [69]. The δ is meant to differentiate physical effects coming from the laser light, as opposed to electric and magnetic fields that are deliberately applied through other means.

when we calculate the magnitude of the actual B -field, i.e.

$$|B_{actual}| = \sqrt{(B_x)^2 + (+\Delta B_z)^2}, \quad (2.49)$$

where ΔB_z is the additional B -field caused by the circularly polarized pump light that is propagating along the z -axis (I have kept to the coordinate axes specified in Fig. 2.8). We can do some manipulation on Eq. 2.49, such that

$$|B_{actual}| \approx \sqrt{(B_x)^2 + (B_z)^2 + 2B_z\Delta B_z} \quad (2.50)$$

$$\approx \sqrt{(B_x)^2 + (B_z)^2} \left(1 + \frac{B_z\Delta B_z}{(B_x)^2 + (B_z)^2} \right), \quad (2.51)$$

thus as $|B_{app}| = \sqrt{(B_x)^2 + (B_z)^2}$,

$$\Delta B \approx \sqrt{(B_x)^2 + (B_z)^2} \left(\frac{B_z\Delta B_z}{(B_x)^2 + (B_z)^2} \right) \quad (2.52)$$

$$= \frac{B_z\Delta B_z}{\sqrt{(B_x)^2 + (B_z)^2}} \quad (2.53)$$

$$= \frac{B_z\Delta B_z}{|B_{app}|}, \quad (2.54)$$

which is a first order sensitivity to AC light shift.

2.5.2 AC Light Shift in Gen II

The crucial improvement in Gen II is that the circularly polarized pump beam is perpendicular to \mathbf{B}_{app} . Retaining the coordinate axes of Fig. 2.7, our \mathbf{B}_{app} is along the z -axis, whereas the pump beam is propagating along the x -axis.

Thus in this case,

$$|B_{\text{actual}}| = \sqrt{(\Delta B_x)^2 + (B_y)^2 + (B_z)^2} \quad (2.55)$$

$$= \sqrt{(B_y)^2 + (B_z)^2} \sqrt{1 + \frac{(\Delta B_x)^2}{(B_y)^2 + (B_z)^2}} \quad (2.56)$$

$$\approx \sqrt{(B_y)^2 + (B_z)^2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{(\Delta B_x)^2}{(B_y)^2 + (B_z)^2} \right), \quad (2.57)$$

hence

$$\Delta B \approx \sqrt{(B_y)^2 + (B_z)^2} \left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{(\Delta B_x)^2}{(B_y)^2 + (B_z)^2} \right) \quad (2.58)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \frac{(\Delta B_x)^2}{\sqrt{(B_y)^2 + (B_z)^2}} \quad (2.59)$$

$$\approx \frac{1}{2} \frac{(\Delta B_x)^2}{|B_{\text{app}}|}, \quad (2.60)$$

which is second order in $\Delta B/B_{\text{app}}$. For reasonable values of $\Delta B/B_{\text{app}}$ this term should be more than an order of magnitude smaller than Eq. 2.54. Thus, we hope that this innovation will allow us to obtain an order of magnitude better accuracy in Gen II compared to Gen I.

2.5.3 Tensor Light Shifts

The last kind of light shift from Eq. 2.48 is δE_2 , the *tensor light shift*, is analogous to the effect of a static electric field \mathbf{E}_2 applied to the atom, giving rise to a tensor Stark shift. This shift is more difficult to calculate as we must actually determine the electric field applied by the light to the atom. There is also the fact that in our basic setup, we do not distinguish between

magnetic sublevels. The shift ΔE for a Zeeman sublevel M is calculated to be proportional to the Legendre polynomial P_2 (Problem 2.11 of [70]), i.e.,

$$\Delta E(M) \propto \frac{3 \cos^2 \theta - 1}{2} [3M^2 - F(F + 1)], \quad (2.61)$$

where θ is the angle between \mathbf{E}_2 to \mathbf{B}_{app} . Thus, when we set $P_2(\theta) = 0$, that is, $\theta \approx 54.7^\circ$, we will minimize the effect of this light shift. We anticipate that this effect will be smaller than the Zeeman light shift. At this time, we are still experimentally investigating the extent of the latter, so the tensor light shift will be a topic to be explored only in the future.

2.6 Two Pumping and Probing Schemes

In the process of implementing Gen II, there are two possible alternative pumping and probing schemes that we are investigating. Both of these utilize the same optical geometry of Fig. 2.7, but differ in the method of collecting data. The main aim of this thesis is to explore both schemes and eventually determine which one will be more advantageous for improving our bounds on LRSSIs.

2.6.1 Scheme I: Pump then Probe (PTP)

In this scheme, the probe light is always on, and the photodetectors are connected directly to the computer via the DAQ (Data Acquisition System). In a single run, we turn on the modulated pump light for an amount of time

until the polarization is fully pumped, usually about 200 ms or so for our Cs cells. The pump light is then turned off, and the atom will keep oscillating for a while due to the Larmor precession of the atomic polarization, which is reflected in the oscillation of the probe light detected by the detectors. However, the oscillation decays with a time constant T_2 . As has been mentioned before, it is the difference channel (between the two orthogonal linear polarizations) that we analyze. An example of a trace recorded by the DAQ for a single run is shown in Fig. 2.10. During the portion from $t = 0$ to $t = 200$ ms, we see an expanding signal, which indicates the atoms are gradually being pumped into a coherent polarization. In this trace, the pumping is stopped at $t = 200$ ms as we found out that pumping longer does not further expand the signal, indicating that this amount of time is about just enough to achieve a stable state of polarization. For the next 400 ms, we let the signal decay and record the oscillations. This portion of the trace is fitted in LabVIEW to a decaying function in the form

$$y = A_3 e^{-t/A_4} \sin(A_1 t + A_2), \quad (2.62)$$

where A_1 , the frequency of the modulation, is the main fit parameter that we are concerned about.⁷ Note that A_4 is equal to the lifetime T_2 . We repeat this process over many runs, monitoring any changes in A_1 .

The main advantage of the PTP scheme is that the pump light is off when the probing takes place. Thus in principle, we should not be too vulnerable

⁷We could have added an additional fit parameter A_5 for a linear offset to Eq. 2.62, but LabVIEW was able to fit without specifying this parameter, so we omitted it.

Figure 2.10: A trace recorded by the DAQ for the difference channel of the bottom Cs cell, from a single PTP run performed on April 10, 2015. The x -axis has units of tenths of milliseconds.

to small deviations in the angle between pump and probe beams, for example. A disadvantage is lower statistical sensitivity compared to the other method (which we discovered early in our investigations), and less ability to continually monitor the magnetometer due to the need to switch constantly between pumping and probing.

2.6.2 Scheme II: Continuous Pumping and Probing (CPP)

In this scheme, both the pump and probe laser are constantly on (with the pump light constantly modulated at the Larmor frequency). The atoms are thus in a steady state of polarization. The difference signal for the two Cs cells are each sent to a dual-phase lock-in amplifier. The lock-ins' reference is the same signal that generates the modulation of the pump intensity. The lock-ins convert the frequency into phase θ and amplitude R (more extensive details are discussed in Ch. 3 and Appendix A). We thus monitor the phase over time. In

order to convert changes in the phase to changes in the frequency (essentially, finding out the value of $d\nu/d\theta$), we do a test where we change the frequency of the pump modulation by a small amount (0.5 Hz higher and lower in our standard procedure) and see how much the phase changes from this artificial tinkering. This allows us to calibrate the sensitivity of each cell.

The main advantage of the CPP scheme is that its statistics are much better than PTP (in fact, about an order of magnitude better in our investigation, as will be seen in Ch. 6). It also allows for more continuous, uniform monitoring of the magnetometer's B -field, and we will not encounter curve-fitting failures like we sometimes do in the case of PTP, as we are just monitoring values of the phase. The main disadvantage, however, is that we anticipate it to be very sensitive to changes in the angle between the pump and probe lasers. This is a serious concern, as in the actual experiment, the apparatus will be rotated 180° every few minutes, and from our past experiences with the Gen I apparatus, small shifts in the directions of the laser light are to be expected. Thus, a major objective in the thesis is to see whether increased sensitivity to systematics will outweigh the inherent statistical advantages of CPP.

2.7 Target Sensitivity

Before we delve into experimental investigation of the two schemes, it is crucial to explicitly spell out the level of improvement we are hoping to achieve. At the 1 sigma level, Gen I managed to achieve a sensitivity of

$$\Delta v_N^{\text{Hg}} < 0.7 \mu\text{Hz}. \tag{2.63}$$

Our target is an order of magnitude better than this, i.e.

$$\Delta v_N^{\text{Hg}} < 0.07 \mu\text{Hz}. \quad (2.64)$$

First, we consider the gyromagnetic ratios of Cs and Hg, which determine their Larmor precession frequency. They are

$$\gamma_{\text{Cs}} \approx 350\text{kHz/G} \quad (2.65)$$

$$\gamma_{\text{Hg}} \approx 759\text{Hz/G}, \quad (2.66)$$

and because the magnetic field is locked to the Cs cells, while we are observing the Hg cells, we are concerned with the ratio between the two gyromagnetic ratios, i.e.

$$\frac{\gamma_{\text{Cs}}}{\gamma_{\text{Hg}}} \approx 461. \quad (2.67)$$

Thus, when we are working with only Cs cells, we will need to achieve a sensitivity of

$$\Delta v_N^{\text{Cs}} < 0.07 \times 461 = 32 \mu\text{Hz}. \quad (2.68)$$

Now the relation between the standard error SE, sample standard deviation σ and number of data points N is

$$\text{SE} = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{N}}. \quad (2.69)$$

Assume that we would want to make a single measurement after about a week ($\sim 10,000 \text{ min} = 6 \times 10^5 \text{ s}$) of running data, and that t_{data} is the time in seconds

needed to take one data point. Thus we would want the standard deviation of the Cs frequency, $\sigma_{\nu_{\text{Cs}}}$ to be

$$\sigma_{\nu_{\text{Cs}}} < 32 \times 10^{-6} \times \sqrt{\frac{6 \times 10^5}{t_{\text{data}}}} \quad (2.70)$$

Thus this is the target we are to keep in mind as we investigate both the PTP and CPP schemes (which have different values of t_{data}) in the following chapters.

2.8 Summary

In this chapter, we have fully described the physics behind our experimental apparatus that allow us to look for the spin-spin interactions described in Ch. 1. We have seen how spin couples to magnetic fields, and how magnetic fields cause Larmor precession in the atoms of the co-magnetometer, making it possible to look for spin-spin interactions by monitoring their precession frequency. We have explained how we monitor this frequency by optical pumping and probing, and how our new optical geometry is projected to perform better with regards to AC light shift, which was the limitation for Gen I. In the next chapter, we shall describe more technical details about the equipment used to perform the experiment described in this chapter.

Chapter 3

Experimental Apparatus

In this chapter we shall describe and discuss the various pieces of equipment that make up our apparatus. We shall note any differences between Gen I and Gen II along the way.

3.1 Rotating Table and the Test Table

We ultimately hope to be able to implement Gen II on a rotating table, as with Gen I. A photo of the rotating-table apparatus is shown in Fig. 3.1. There are many challenges, however, to working directly on the rotating table apparatus, as the vertical layout requires one to climb a ladder in order to take the cells in and out, and we would also have to find a way to mount the photo-detectors on top of the cylindrical cans¹. Attempting to surmount all these physical challenges while also exploring a new optical geometry would

¹In the rest of this chapter, “cans” refers to the cylindrical layers of magnetic shielding that encase the cells and the cell mounting.

be time-consuming and difficult. Hence, for the current experimental stage of the project, we switched to a horizontal test apparatus (Fig. 3.2), allowing for easy access to the optics as well as the cells.

Figure 3.1: Photo of apparatus on rotating table. Most of the original optics at the base have been removed and so are not visible here.

Other than its orientation, the test apparatus is similar in most respects to the rotating table apparatus. An optics table is setup on one side. On the

other side of the cans we have mounted scaffolding to allow us to easily pull the mount for the cells and magnetic coils in and out of the cans. Once the cells are mounted and the cans are sealed, this end of the table supports a second optical table with the probe photodetectors. Three layers of magnetic shielding protect the internal support structure which houses the cells. At the ends, each cylindrical shield has its own metal cap that is perforated with some holes to let light, fiber optic cables, wires, and mirror-adjusting rods to come through to the outside. When all three caps are installed, these holes are roughly concentric. The test apparatus is a relic from the old electron EDM experiment, performed in the Hunter lab during the 1990s [71].

Figure 3.2: Photo of test apparatus, with the optics table in the foreground and the horizontal cans visible in the background.

3.2 Atomic Vapor Cells

3.2.1 New Cell Design

An important factor in boosting the apparatus' level of sensitivity is prolonging the spin relaxation time T_2 , as it gives us more time to interrogate the spin precession before it decays away. However, it is also the case that having a shorter lifetime allows one to take more data points. The frequency resolution η in the measurement of the frequency follows the relation

$$\eta \propto \frac{w}{\sqrt{N}}, \quad (3.1)$$

where w is the line width in the frequency spectrum and N is the number of measurements. Now,

$$w \propto \frac{1}{T_2} \quad (3.2)$$

and

$$N \propto \frac{T_{\text{int}}}{T_2} \quad (3.3)$$

where T_{int} is the integration time, i.e. the amount of total time spent taking data. so

$$\eta \propto \frac{1}{\sqrt{T_{\text{int}}T_2}} \quad (3.4)$$

Thus, a gain of p in T_2 will only result in a gain \sqrt{p} in η .

An atomic vapor cell typically consists of a main cell bulb where most of atomic vapor is contained, a reservoir which contains the substance in liquid form, and a stem connecting the reservoir and the bulb. Often, as in our case,

the cell walls are coated with wax that dramatically reduces the collisional relaxation with the walls. The stem is a hazardous area for the atoms, as any that stray inside will rapidly become depolarized from colliding with the stem walls. The probability that an atom will enter the stem cell region P_{stem} can be calculated by

$$P_{\text{stem}} \propto \frac{A_{\text{stem}}}{A_{\text{surface}}}, \quad (3.5)$$

where A_{stem} is the cross-sectional area of the stem and A_{surface} is the rest of the surface area of the interior of the cell. A higher value of P_{stem} will result in a shorter T_2 .

Besides the size of the stem, another factor that directly affects T_2 is the size of the cell. A larger cell will result in fewer collisions between the atoms and the cells, and thus a longer lifetime. However, in our case, there are limitations to increasing the size of the cell as large cells will result in more inhomogeneity of the magnetic field experienced by the different cells.

The Gen I Cs vapor cells had a lifetime of ~ 20 ms. They were cylindrically shaped with a diameter of $\sim 2''$, and a stem with diameter $\sim 0.25''$ (Fig. 3.3).

Figure 3.3: Diagram of old Gen I Cs cells.

The three new Gen II vapor cells have superior lifetimes ranging from 40-100 ms. The cell walls are coated with alkene 1-nonadecene anti-relaxation coating, and evacuated with residual pressure $\approx 10^{-6}$ torr. They are prepared using the procedure outlined in [72]. The stem is much narrower (outer diameter $\sim 0.125''$) and longer than the Gen I cells (see Fig. 3.4). The L-shaped design of the stem and reservoir also further isolates the latter from the main part of the cell. The four rectangular sides are almost completely flat. These four surfaces with good optical quality allow the pump and probe beams to pass with little distortion.

Figure 3.4: Diagram of new Gen II Cs cells. The outer diameter of the stem is $\sim 0.125''$ for all the cells. The length of the stem and reservoir varies slightly for the three cells.

3.2.2 Cell Mounting

Currently, the two Cs cells are housed in a mounting made of plexiglass, as seen in Fig. 3.5. The mounting was originally built for the stack of four cells in the EDM experiment. A diagram of the central interaction area is shown in Fig. 3.6. A large circular quarter wave plate (QWP) is mounted on one side of the cell, which converts the linearly polarized pump light into circularly

polarized light. Right next to the QWP and further away from the center, a wall is mounted at $\sim 45^\circ$. Small adjustable mirrors are mounted on this wall, one for each cell. They reflect the pump light (which initially comes in at an acute angle into the cans) such that it goes straight through the cell and orthogonal to the probe light. On the opposite side, some scaffolding allows us to connect a fiber optic cable at just the right height for each cell. The pump light goes through the QWP, through the cells, and into these cables which are connected to a photodiode circuit outside the cans, allowing us to monitor the intensity of the pump light.

Figure 3.5: Photo of cell mount (side view), here shown when not inside the cans.

The bottom cell is situated at the center of mounting. It sits on top of a piece of foam which has a part cut out to accommodate the L-shaped stem. A thin piece of rubber separates it and the top cell, which is placed upside down. Another similar piece of foam protects the top cell's stem and also allows us

to screw down the square piece of fiber glass on the top that holds the entire structure together.

Figure 3.6: Diagram of cell mount (top view). QWP stands for quarter wave plate. Although the mount for the pump monitor fiber optics have 4 stories (as the cell mount was originally designed to house 4 stacked cells), only the middle two are currently used in our setup.

3.2.3 Lifetime Measurements

In May-June 2014, we embarked on a comparison of the lifetimes of the old and new vapor cells. This was accomplished using the PTP method, already outlined in Sec. 2.6.1. (More technical details of the procedure will be discussed in Ch. 4.) Multiple pump-then-probe cycles were performed, the traces recorded, averaged, and then fit to a decay curve using Mathematica's FindFit

curve-fitting function.² The results are shown in Tab. 3.1. Based on this, we picked the “brown dot” and “short stem” to be put into the apparatus when experimenting with two cells for the first time.

Cell No.	Nickname	T_2 (ms)
1	“Brown dot”	93.3
2	“Skinny”	66.1
3	“Short stem”	87.5

Table 3.1: Measured values of T_2 taken in July-August 2014, obtained by tuning the probe laser 3 GHz off resonance and using the PTP scheme. Only one cell was measured at a time. Note that when we inserted “brown dot” and “short stem” into the cans, the lifetime of “short stem” dropped to ~ 40 ms.

We also did some preliminary investigations on the relation between lifetime and pump/probe intensity. The intensity of the pump or probe was altered using a set of glass filters. An example of the results are shown in Tabs. 3.2 and 3.3. In general, decreasing the pump or probe intensity slightly improved the lifetimes. For the case of decreasing probe intensity, this is expected, as a lower probe intensity means less depolarizing of the atoms. However, lowering the probe intensity also increased the noise, requiring more measurements in order to be able to successfully fit the trace.

In the case of decreasing pump intensity, the increase in T_2 is unexpected, as in the PTP method, the pump is turned off during the probing, and the assumption is that the cell has been fully pumped after 200 ms. Thus, changing the pump attenuation should not have an effect on the lifetime. Based on this finding, we believe that this result may have been caused by peculiarities in the

²Eventually, we would realize LabVIEW’s native curve-fitting routines are faster than those of Mathematica.

curve-fitting algorithm. We encountered similar odd phenomena when later doing systematics investigations on PTP (Ch. 5).

Probe attenuation	T_2 (ms)		
	”Brown dot”	”Skinny”	”Short stem”
None (100 %)	93.3	66.1	87.5
78%	-	67.7	90.4
23%	-	67.7	97.4

Table 3.2: The effect of attenuating the probe laser on T_2 .

Pump attenuation	T_2 (ms)		
	”Brown dot”	”Skinny”	”Short stem”
None (100 %)	93.3	66.1	87.5
80%	93.5	67.4	88.5
32%	94.2	68.1	-
20%	96.5	68.2	91.8

Table 3.3: The effect of attenuating the pump laser on T_2 .

One remaining mystery that we encountered is how the lifetime of cell “skinny” decreased sharply from ~ 100 ms to ~ 40 ms after we put it inside the cans together with cell “brown tip”. Initially, we thought that this was due to the cell being placed upside down, resulting in some liquid Cs leaking from the reservoir and flowing into the main bulb. If this hypothesis were true, then the lifetime would steadily decrease over several weeks as more Cs flowed down the stem. However, the new lifetime remained stable at ~ 40 ms for the next few months (September 2014-April 2015). Hence there is further investigation pending for this phenomenon. A straightforward thing to do would be to try reversing the top and bottom cells and see if any changes in the lifetime occurs. As of now (April 2015), we are busy investigating systematics with the current configuration, so this will remain something to do only in the next few months.

3.3 Magnetic Field Coils

3.3.1 Helmholtz Coils

Three pairs of Helmholtz coils, one for each dimension, encircle the cell mounting structure inside the cans. Each pair contains 2×10 turns of copper wire. Currently only one pair is used as we are not yet locking the B -field to the Cs frequency. This is the pair with the coils in the xy -plane, creating a homogeneous B -field in the z -direction. Thus, our z -axis is orthogonal to the plane of the floor of the laboratory. For this pair, the upper set of turns are spaced $\sim 6''$ from the bottom set. The upper and bottom sets are connected in series, and the two ends of the cable are connected to a circuit that allows both coarse and fine B -field control.

3.3.2 Fine Magnetic Field Control

The voltage across the external power supply can be modified by turning a knob, but for practical purposes we always keep it set to a base voltage $V_{\text{base}} = 9.74$ V. It is connected to a simple circuit that allows us to finely control the B -field (Fig. 3.7). We set $R_{\text{base}} = 1$ k Ω and $R_{\text{fine}} = 100$ k Ω . When we apply a voltage V_{fine} of several volts, as $R_{\text{fine}} \gg R_{\text{base}}$, a small amount of additional current will be added to the current from V_{base} , slightly increasing the B -field.

Initially, we connected V_{fine} directly to either a DAQ output or to an auxiliary voltage output on one of our SRS dual-phase lock-in amplifiers. However, when we were taking data using CPP, we found that the level of magnetic

noise sharply increased, even when we set $V_{\text{fine}} = 0$ V. This may have been a result of *ground loops* in the circuit. A ground loop occurs when several circuit components that are supposed to be at ground (i.e. $V = 0$ V) are actually at slightly different voltages. To solve this problem, we connect V_{fine} to an opto-isolator unit before connecting it to the lock-in amplifier.

Figure 3.7: Diagram of circuit that allows fine control of the B -field inside the cans.

An opto-isolator unit contains an LED that converts voltage into light, and a photodiode that detects the light. Thus, electrical signals can be transmitted between two electrically isolated circuits. Using an opto-isolator, the magnetic noise is no worse than if we disconnect V_{fine} completely.

3.3.3 General Operational Conditions

On a typical day, we operate with a Larmor frequency of ~ 2100 Hz for Cs. As we know that $\gamma_{\text{Cs}} \approx 350$ Hz/mG, this is magnetic field of ~ 6 mG. Periodically, we degauss the cans by running several hundreds of amperes of current through

an annealing copper wire that goes through the cans. This is usually done after we have fixed or tampered with the cell mounting, and results in small changes of tens of Hz in the Larmor frequency.

3.4 Lasers

We shall now discuss the lasers that are used to pump and probe the atomic vapor cells, including features that allow thermal stabilization and frequency locking. For the case of Cs, Gen II uses the same type of lasers as Gen I, and thus we will not discuss the Cs lasers in too much detail, as a more complete treatment is available in Stein's thesis [56]. Most of the discussion here is based on this reference.

3.4.1 Cesium Laser System

Two separate external cavity diode lasers (ECDL) are used for pumping and probing the Cs cells. Both lasers work in exactly the same way. Laser light is produced by placing a Thor Labs LP880-SF3 (rated at 3 mW) laser diode inside a cavity with a diffraction grating (Fig. 3.8). The diffraction grating is attached to a piezoelectric chip that allows us to finely modify the length of the cavity by applying a voltage to it. It is configured such that the first order diffraction is reflected back in the cavity, providing optical feedback. The zeroth order diffraction is deflected out of the cavity and becomes the output

beam. First order diffraction in a diffraction grating follows the relationship

$$\sin \theta_l = \frac{\lambda}{2d}, \quad (3.6)$$

where θ_l is the “Littrow Angle” and d is the grid spacing. In our case, we want $\lambda = 894$ nm, and our diffraction grating has a density of 1200 lines/mm, giving us $\theta_l = 32.4^\circ$. The length of the cavity further determines the wavelength λ of the light, as expressed in the relation

$$l = \frac{n\lambda}{2}, \quad (3.7)$$

where l is the length of the cavity and n is an integer. This equation applies only for constructively interfering light; light that destructively interferes is not successfully amplified, thus keeping our laser single mode. In order to tune the wavelength, we only need to change the voltage applied to the piezo. Coarser changes can be made by controlling screws that mechanically modify the length of the cavity and the angle of the grating. When we are tuning the frequency, we feed the light into a custom-made wavemeter that measures the wavelength by comparing it to that of a thermally stabilized He-Ne laser.³ The power of the Cs laser coming out of the laser cavity is ~ 1.5 mW. It is also roughly vertically polarized (i.e., aligned along the z -axis). Some of this light is diverted to the external Cs reference cell (as we will see in Fig. 3.11). By the time it goes into the cans, the power of the pump laser is ~ 500 μ W.

³We also used the laser of this wavemeter for probe laser locking.

Figure 3.8: Basic diagram of an ECDL. Adapted from [56].

3.4.2 Frequency Locking

The wavelength of a laser can easily drift over time due to a number of factors, such as fluctuations in temperature, humidity, voltages/currents, and also mechanical changes in any part of the laser cavity or other parts of the apparatus. In a precision measurement experiment like this, it is important to be able to counteract these fluctuations and keep the laser wavelength constant and locked to the resonant wavelength of the atomic transition we are using. This is accomplished by our frequency⁴ locking mechanism. The locking mechanism takes advantage of the absorption profile of Cs using a single-phase lock-in amplifier. To make this process easier, we have a large, separate vapor cell of cesium for each laser on the optics table that is used solely for the pur-

⁴In the rest of this section I shall use frequency and wavelength interchangeably as they are simply related by $c = \lambda\nu$.

pose of locking, dubbed the *reference cell* (Fig. 3.9). The details of this locking scheme have been covered elsewhere, such as in [56]. A longer explanation is available in Appendix A.

Figure 3.9: Photo of Cs reference cell. Here we can also see the photodetector that receives the light after it has shone through the cell.

3.4.3 Thermal Stabilization

As our laser is operating in the nanometer range, even small thermal fluctuations in the room would be enough to cause the metal laser cavity to expand or contract, causing instability in the emitted laser wavelength. To counteract this, the external cavity is placed inside a casing that has two levels, or stages, of temperature control. Each stage consists of a set of thermistors that measure the temperature and a set of thermoelectric devices to adjust the temperature accordingly (Fig. 3.10). Stage 1 acts as the coarse temperature control, with thermistors placed beneath the laser cavity, on top of Invar block on which the cavity rests. Stage 2 is the fine temperature control, with ther-

mistors placed directly underneath the laser diode. The entire setup is then encased in several layers of thermal insulation. Both stages of temperature control are always on 24/7, allowing us to reliably turn the laser on and off any time and always reach the desired wavelength.

Figure 3.10: Photo of Cs pump laser, where we can see the external cavity and various thermal-stabilization components. Normally the structure is covered with two layers of thermally insulating casing.

3.4.4 Mercury Laser

The wavelength needed for our Hg laser is 254 nm, in the ultraviolet range. This is more difficult to generate than the infrared light for the Cs transitions. The current laser we have in the lab used in Gen I also starts with an ECDL at the Littrow angle. However, to reach the desired wavelength two frequency

doubling cavities with different crystals are needed. In Gen I, the experimental cells had buffer gas inside them which made them have different absorption line centers compared to the evacuated external reference cells. This made it impossible to lock the laser using the same scheme as the Cs laser. So instead of locking to the center dip of the absorption profile, it was locked to the side [56]. As of April 2015, we are not in the stage of working with Hg cells yet, so it is still unclear what changes will be made for Gen II. We are anticipating the arrival of improved Hg cells from the Heckel lab at the University of Washington. Because we do not have a second Hg laser, it is likely that we will use the same beam to pump and probe the Hg cell, something which we tried with the Cs cells in the early stages of this thesis work but found difficult to do.

3.5 Optical Setup

We have already covered several aspects of the setup of the optical table, such as the reference cell used for frequency locking. There are only a few other components to describe before our pump and probe optical setup is complete. Fig. 3.11 shows a full diagram of all the components on the optics table that we will discuss, featuring the reference cells, the linear polarizers, the Pockels cell, the beam dividers, etc.

- Legend:
- | | | |
|-----------------------|--------------------------|-----------------------|
| 1 Pump ECDL | 7 Linear polarizer (hor) | 13 Probe ref cell |
| 2 Astigmatism prism | 8 Beam divider | 14 Probe ref detector |
| 3 Pump ref cell | 9 To QWP and cells | 15 HWP |
| 4 Pump ref detector | 10 Probe ECDL | 16 Beam divider |
| 5 Variable attenuator | 11 Astigmatism prism | 17 Linear polarizers |
| 6 Pockels cell | 12 To Fabry-Perot | 18 To cells |

Figure 3.11: Full diagram of the optics table.

3.5.1 Pockels Cell

In order to modulate the intensity of the pump beam at the Larmor frequency, which is essential for the pumping process (as we have explained in detail in Sec. 2.6.1), we shine the pump beam through a Pockels cell (No. 6 in Fig. 3.11). Such a cell makes use of the Pockels effect, where a medium becomes birefringent when an electric field is applied to it. Our Pockels cell is rated for a voltage of 300 – 400 V. We initially send a square wave with an amplitude of 1 – 3 volts and 20% duty cycle into a voltage amplifier. This wave can come directly from a function generator (as is the case when we are operating on the CPP scheme), or programmed through the DAQ (as in the PTP scheme). The voltage amplifier draws upon a power supply and amplifies the voltage wave such that it is on the level of hundreds of volts, and then sends it to the Pockels cell. Only then will the cell modulate its birefringence.

Following the Pockels cell is a linear polarizer (No. 7). Now, the pump light is initially roughly vertically polarized coming out of the ECDL. When we are about to begin data collection, this linear polarizer is rotated such that it is positioned horizontally, thus initially blocking the light. When a voltage is applied to the Pockels cell, its birefringence will rotate the polarization of the light, such that it is not fully vertical, allowing some of it to pass through the linear polarizer.

3.5.2 Dividing the Beam

We have two Cs cells in our apparatus, and both of these have to be pumped and probed. It is important that the light pumping and probing the two cells

be as similar as possible, especially the frequency. In order to do this, we divide the beam using a 50/50 beamsplitter placed at $\sim 45^\circ$ angle (Fig. 3.12, and also Nos. 8 and 16 in Fig. 3.11). While the beamsplitter is rated for 50/50 (because we want our two beams to be as identical as possible), in practice, about 25% of the beam is reflected while the rest is transmitted through into the bottom cell, because of the incident polarization on the beamsplitter. A mirror is placed at the same angle as the beamsplitter a short distance above it, reflecting the beam and giving us two parallel beams that go into the top and bottom Cs cells. This setup is used for both the probe and pump beams.

Figure 3.12: Diagram showing how we divide the pump and probe beams into two parallel beams, each of which goes to one of the Cs cells.

3.5.3 Probe Polarization

For optical rotation to work well, the probe must have good linear polarization. This is accomplished by the use of two Glan-Thompson polarizers (one for the beam going into each cell), housed in a custom-machined mount made from aluminum (Fig. 3.14, and No. 17 in Fig. 3.11). The mount is designed such that the separation between the two polarizers is the same as the vertical distance between the centers of the two Cs cells when they are stacked together on

Figure 3.13: Photo of beam divider, in this example for the probe beam. Both the beam splitter and the mirror are held in place using a crossbar attachment to a standard optical mount.

the cell mounting inside ($\sim 0.5''$). The mount allows us to rotate and secure the polarizers to whatever angle we want. In our initial runs, we adjust the polarization until it is at $\sim 45^\circ$ from the B -field (which is along the z -axis). This is done by minimizing the difference channel on the probe detectors (which shall be described more fully in the next section). We anticipate that when we are trying to get rid of tensor light shifts in the future, the polarization will be adjusted to the “magic angle” of 54.7° that minimizes the tensor light shift (Chapter 2.5.3). When the third Hg cell is incorporated, we will have to craft a new, three-level mount that will allow linearly polarized light to go through all three cells.

Figure 3.14: Photo of probe Glan-Thompson linear polarizers in a custom-made two-story mount.

3.5.4 Probe Detectors

The linearly polarized probe light, having been optically rotated after passing through the cells, comes out of the cans through the holes on the caps of the cans. It then goes through a beamsplitting cube sitting on a shelf that separates the polarization into two orthogonal linear components (Fig. 3.15). Each of the two components is received by a separate Hamamatsu S5390-08 photodiode. The two photodiodes are connected to a circuit board that has three output channels: PD1, PD2 (the two original linear components) and DIFF, the difference between the two components. The circuit board is housed within a custom-made aluminum box that protects it from any external electronics noise (Fig. 3.16). There are currently two of these boxes, one each for the light from the top and bottom cells. Both draw power from the same external power supply. We later discovered that replacing this with independent 9-volt batteries for each board improved electronics noise.

Figure 3.15: Diagram of the splitting of the probe beam into two channels on the circuit board.

The two detector boxes are mounted on an optics table and a cutout cardboard box covers both of them. We later draped a piece of black cloth between

Figure 3.16: Photo of probe detector boxes, each featuring a shelf that holds the beamsplitting cube and showing the two Hamamatsu photodiodes that are attached to the circuit board inside.

the caps and the box to decrease the noise from the room light. All of the outputs from the probe detector circuit boards are connected to the National Instruments DAQ system on the computer, for a total of 6 channels (three for each cell).

3.5.5 Laser Attenuation

One of the features we wanted to test the apparatus for was possible systematic error arising from changes in the intensity of the lasers. When doing the lifetime measurements, the attenuation was accomplished by simply placing a series of colored glass filters after the beam. This, however, is not sufficient for systematic varying of the intensity. Thus when actually studying the systematics (Chs. 5 and 6) we added features that allowed us to do this. For the

pump, we put a variable attenuator that had a wheel with graduated levels of aluminum on it. One increased or decreased the attenuation by spinning the wheel. This is placed after the Pockels cell and the linear polarizer and right before the light is divided into two.

Earlier, we had experimented with varying the intensity by adding additional optics, such that after exiting the Pockels cell, the pump light would go through the original linear polarizer, a half-wave plate (HWP), and an additional linear polarizer orthogonal to the first one. Rotating the orientation of the HWP would change the balance of the linear components and thus the intensity. The advantage of this method is that the light would not be translated after being attenuated, something which might happen with attenuators which rely on blocking the light with layers of material instead of changing the polarization. However, we found that using this method did not result in a noticeable change in the behavior of the system compared to using the aluminum variable attenuator, and we ended up using the latter method.

For the probe laser, we attenuated the beam by placing a HWP right before the beam was divided into two. This would affect the balance of the light that went through the Glan-Thompson linear polarizers, thus affecting the intensity of the light going through the cells.

3.6 Data Acquisition and Other Devices

The CPP method for our experiment requires the use of dual-phase lock-in amplifiers, one for each cell. We utilize SRS SR850 lock-ins that were also

used in Gen I. Only two are needed at the moment; a third lock-in is used to control the fine B -field control voltage. We connect the SYNC input on the lock-ins to the output of an SRS DS345 function generator. We also feed in the DC signal from the experiment by connecting the DIFF channel to the front input of the lock-in. The two lock-ins are connected to the computer via a GPIB connector.

The SRS DS345 function generator is also connected to the signal amplifier. With the flip of a switch, we can change this so that the signal amplifier is connected to the DAQ instead, which generates the waves when operating on PTP mode. Thus it is easy to switch between the CPP and PTP configurations.

The probe detectors and pump monitor BNC cables are connected to a National Instruments Data Acquisition (NI DAQ) system that communicates with the computer through a PCI Express card (NI PCIe-6361). This card is also used to digitally generate sine waves when running on PTP mode. Input from the Fabry-Perot cavity (which will be discussed in the next section) is received on an separate DAQ system connected via USB (NI USB-6343). The Stanford DS345 function generator, the dual-phase lock-ins for CPP mode, and the single phase lock-ins for Cs laser frequency locking are connected to the computer via a GPIB card. The software LabVIEW is used to electronically control our devices and receive and process data. More detailed information about the software aspect of the electronics (i.e., how signal is gathered and processed) will be in Chapter 4.

3.7 Fabry-Perot Cavity

As we have mentioned before, as we are tuning the probe laser ~ 3 GHz off line resonance, we are in a flat region of the absorption curve, so it is not possible to take advantage of it to lock the laser. Instead, we use a Fabry-Perot (F-P) cavity that reads the wavelength of the laser and compares it to the known wavelength of a stabilized He-Ne laser. The Fabry-Perot cavity we use was originally built by the DeMille lab at Yale University. The design of the cavity is similar to the one built by Chu Teng '13 in the Hanneke lab, and a fuller discussion of the cavity can be found in [73].

3.7.1 Fabry-Perot Cavity Basics

An F-P cavity contains a confocal pair of concave mirrors (Fig. 3.17). The two mirrors have the same radius R and in order for them to be confocal, the distance L between them has to be equal to R . An input beam enters the cavity, resulting in four output beams (here labeled as front and rear outputs 1 and 2). Due to the confocal design, as seen in the diagram, the input beam does not have to be aligned with the focus in order to be reflected out. (It is still important that the beam travels parallel to the table.) A beam travels a distance of $\sim 4L$ inside the cavity before retracing its path. Constructive interference occurs when

$$\frac{n\lambda}{4} = L, \quad (3.8)$$

where λ is the wavelength of the light and n is an integer. Like the cavity of our ECDL, the length of the F-P cavity is controlled by a piezoelectric. By

applying a sweeping voltage to the piezo, a range of different wavelengths will be covered and we will see transmission peaks whenever constructive interference occurs. The distance between two adjacent peaks will be $\lambda/4$. In terms of frequency, this is known as the *free spectral range* (FSR), and can be expressed as

$$\text{FSR} = \nu_{n+1} - \nu_n \quad (3.9)$$

$$= \frac{c(n+1)}{4L} - \frac{cn}{4L} \quad (3.10)$$

$$= \frac{c}{4L}. \quad (3.11)$$

In our case, $L \approx 15$ cm, resulting in $\text{FSR} \approx 500$ MHz. Another important parameter in F-P cavities is the *finesse* N_R , defined as

$$N_R = \frac{\text{FSR}}{\text{FWHM}}, \quad (3.12)$$

where FWHM is the full width half maximum of the transmission peaks. N_R is determined by the reflectivity R of the cavity mirrors, and is given by the formula [74]

$$N_R = \frac{\pi\sqrt{R}}{1-R}. \quad (3.13)$$

The above discussion is simplified as it does not take into account the fact that there are actually two components of the mode number n in Eq. 3.8: the axial and transverse mode numbers. The axial mode number is the more familiar one corresponding to a standing wave between the two cavity mirrors, whereas the transverse mode number deals with the laser beam's electric field

Figure 3.17: Diagram of Fabry-Perot cavity, showing the path followed by light entering the cavity. Taken from [73].

profile in the transverse direction. A fuller discussion of F-P cavities taking into account these issues is found in [73].

3.7.2 Locking with an F-P Cavity

In practice, we can use any of the 4 outputs of the F-P cavity to see transmission peaks. It is easiest to use one of the rear outputs as they do not diverge when coming out of the cavity. A diagram of the F-P cavity setup for locking the probe laser is shown in Fig. 3.18, and a photo is shown in Fig. 3.19. Laser beams from our probe ECDL and a stabilized helium-neon (He-Ne) laser enter the cavity, are combined together, go through the F-P cavity, separated again and are received by two photo detectors: PD1 (ECDL channel) and PD2 (He-Ne channel). These outputs are fed into an NI-DAQ system that is separate from the DAQ used for collecting data from the probe detectors. They are read into “Jeff Lock”, a LabVIEW program for frequency locking built by Jeff Ammon of the DeMille group at Yale.

Figure 3.18: Diagram of Fabry-Perot cavity setup. The optics are all stationed on a mobile breadboard. Taken from [73].

Jeff Lock locks the frequency of the probe laser by comparing the transmission peaks of the He-Ne and probe lasers and fixing the latter's position relative to the former. This is done using a PID (proportional-integral-derivative) control algorithm that computes the correction to the system $u(t)$ using the formula

$$u(t) = K_p e(t) + K_i \int e(t) dt + K_d \frac{de}{dt}, \quad (3.14)$$

where $e(t)$ is the tracking error of the system, and K_p , K_i , and K_d are the proportional, integral, and derivative gains for the controller that we set manually. The three terms can be interpreted as corrections based on the present error (P), accumulation of past errors (I), and prediction of future error (D) [75]. The length of the integration in the second term is set manually. The program calculates $e(t)$ by comparing the position of a transmission peak of the probe

laser to the desired position relative to a He-Ne peak, calculates the correction $u(t)$ based on Eq. 3.14 above, specifies a correction voltage to the probe laser cavity piezo, and then waits for the next round of measurement. The process is repeated ad infinitum.

Figure 3.19: Photo of the F-P cavity setup on a mobile breadboard.

3.7.3 Stabilized He-Ne Laser

The He-Ne laser we use as a frequency reference for our F-P cavity was built by Ken Miller in the 1990s. It is actually part of a portable wavemeter that measures the wavelength of a beam by comparing it to the He-Ne wavelength (632.8 nm). In the setup, a commercial He-Ne laser is wrapped in heating tape that allows the system to heat the laser cavity or let it cool as needed. A laser has two orthogonal polarized modes. The ratio between the two modes changes as the cavity length changes. A beam splitter separates the two modes coming out of the laser and feeds them into two separate photodiodes. The system detects whether heating or cooling is needed based on the ratio. This custom-made laser has a stability comparable to commercial stabilized He-Ne

lasers (on the order of several MHz).

3.8 Summary

We have now completed explaining all of the hardware components of our experiment which are needed to accomplish our main task, which is to track the precession frequency of the Cs atoms in the vapor cells by optical pumping and probing. The next chapter will discuss the more programmatic and software aspects of the system, as well as details on the procedures when running on both PTP and CPP.

Chapter 4

Running Procedures

In this chapter, we shall discuss in more detail the actual protocols and standard procedures we perform when we run the experiment in its current configuration using the test apparatus. We will also describe some important features of the LabView programs we use to control the experiment. Here we shall mainly cover the different procedures used for running in the PTP and CPP schemes. A more thorough description of the general operating procedure is in Appendix B.

4.1 Operating on CPP

First we will discuss the specifics of the procedure used to operate using CPP mode. This comprises of firstly setting up the hardware, and secondly executing the LabView program to collect the data.

4.1.1 Setup

We first turn on the Stanford DS-345 function generator. This function generator is connected to the computer via a GPIB (IEEE-488) cable and can generate a waveform of any arbitrary shape programmed by the computer. Typically, we make it generate square waves with a duty cycle of 20% and an amplitude of 1.0 V. An offset of half the amplitude is applied so that the actual modulation is centered at 1.0 V instead of 0 V as the signal amplifier cannot operate at negative voltages. Besides this, we usually also have an additional 0.02 V offset to further prevent excursions into negative voltages.

We turn on the two dual-phase SRS SR850 lock-in amplifiers. They are connected to the computer via GPIB connectors. One of the lock ins (in our case, the one connected for the bottom cell) actually provides the frequency to the DS345 function generator: we set the DS345 to “burst mode” and connect the frequency output from the SR850 to the DS345’s external trigger channel. Burst mode makes the function generator generate a wave upon receiving a rising slope signal from the external trigger. It is also possible to make function generator itself set the frequency, but this method was chosen as it made it possible for the lock-ins to operate using an internal reference frequency. The waves from the function generator are sent to the signal amplifier, amplified to several hundred volts, and sent to the Pockels cell, creating a continuous modulation on the pump beam.

The dual phase lock-ins are connected to the DIFF channels from the two probe photodetectors (one for each Cs cell). The principles of operation for dual-phase lock-ins are similar to the single-phase ones discussed in Ap-

pendix A. The difference is that there are two PSD outputs. The first PSD is the same as in Eq. A.4, but in the second PSD, the signal is multiplied with the reference frequency shifted by $\pi/2$ [76]:

$$V_{\text{PSD1}} = \frac{1}{2} V_{\text{sig}} V_L \cos(\theta_{\text{sig}} - \theta_{\text{ref}}) \approx V_{\text{sig}} \cos \theta = X, \quad (4.1)$$

$$V_{\text{PSD2}} = \frac{1}{2} V_{\text{sig}} V_L \sin(\theta_{\text{sig}} - \theta_{\text{ref}}) \approx V_{\text{sig}} \sin \theta = Y, \quad (4.2)$$

$$(4.3)$$

where $\theta = \theta_{\text{sig}} - \theta_{\text{ref}}$. We thus have two outputs X and Y , which can also be converted to polar coordinates R and θ . R becomes a measure of the signal amplitude that is independent of the phase. In practice, we seek to maximize R to get the most signal. This is how we detect the Larmor frequency: by manually scanning the frequency of the bottom lock-in and seeing which gives the highest value of R . Scanning over a fairly large range will result in a Lorentzian curve that peaks at the Larmor frequency. θ , on the other hand, will trace out an arctangent curve, which is expected as from Eqs. 4.2 and 4.3, $\theta = \arctan(Y/X)$.

4.1.2 Data Collection

The first data collection run begins with a sensitivity test that calibrates how much change in frequency does an amount of change in phase correspond to, or in other words finding $df/d\theta$. Once the pump is modulated at the Larmor frequency, the phase is set to zero. This is to ensure that we are operating in the middle, approximately linear region of the arctangent curve. Initial zeroing

of phase enables us to easily detect changes in the phase; the absolute value of the phase is arbitrary and meaningless in the experiment. The sensitivity test occurs by changing the frequency to 0.5 Hz above and below the Larmor frequency and seeing how the phase changes. The resulting slope becomes the sensitivity. Typically, with the bottom “brown spot” and top “short stem” vapor cells in the apparatus currently (April 2015), we obtain a sensitivity of ~ 30 degrees/Hz for the bottom cell and ~ 15 degrees/Hz for the top cell, which makes sense as the bottom cell lifetime is roughly twice that of the top cell. These sensitivity values can be used to convert changes in phase to changes in frequency, and thus make it possible to compare with the results from PTP.

The actual data collection then commences. We usually set the lock-ins so that they integrate the data received over a period of 60 ms into one single data point that is sent to the computer. There is a pause of 300 ms between each data point to prevent the lock-ins from being overwhelmed with commands. Together with the time it takes for the GPIB to respond and other software delays, it typically takes a total time of $t_{data} \approx 1.1$ s for each data point. The LabView program for CPP collects the data for R and θ , and also records all the other settings of the experiment (frequency, amplitude, duty cycle, etc.). Usually when testing for systematics, we take 20 points with the system configured to a certain setting before changing it. The LabView program automatically calculates important data from the set, mainly the standard deviation and mean of the phase. Even when operating in this scheme, we also record the 6 outputs of the probe detector (PD1, PD2, DIFF for top and bottom cells) and 2 outputs from the pump monitor photodetectors (top and

bottom). These are connected to the computer via the NI PCIe-6361 DAQ system.

4.2 Operating on PTP

We shall now discuss the specifics of the procedure used in operating using the PTP scheme. In contrast to CPP, most of the commands and voltages are generated directly by the DAQ system, so there are few external hardware components that are used other than the DAQ.

When we want to operate on PTP, we first flip a switch so that the signal amplifier input is connected to an output channel from the NI PCIe-6361 DAQ system. For each pump-probe cycle, the LabView program digitally generates a finite number of square pulses at the Larmor frequency. Usually we use a 20% duty cycle like with the CPP method. The waves are sent to the DAQ at a writing frequency of 100 kHz. The DAQ sends them to the signal amplifier which then relays them to the Pockels cell, causing pump modulation. Usually, we pump the cell for 200 ms, resulting in about 400 waves. This is enough to fully pump the atoms to a stable level of polarization.¹

The output of the DAQ is also connected back to an input channel so that we can continuously monitor the waves we are sending in to the DAQ. More importantly, they are connected to an external trigger channel on the DAQ that tells it when to start collecting input data from the probe detectors. It is important that this be consistent, in order for all the traces for each pump-

¹We will later discover that this may not be sufficient to fully reach equilibrium, causing issues when testing for systematics.

probe cycle to line up properly when they are averaged.²

After the pumping is finished, the output voltage on the DAQ is set to an end value, usually zero.³ Usually we set the length of a pump-probe cycle to 600 ms ($= t_{data}$), such that the probing is done for 400 ms after the pumping stops. During this time, the DAQ is instructed to read the input from the 6 channels of the probe detector outputs and the 2 pump monitors at a rate of 10 kHz. This results in 6000 points being recorded, and a decay curve like Fig. 2.10.

The LabView program then takes the decaying portion of the curve (after the pumping stops, which is 4000 points long) and fits a function of the form of Eq. 2.62 using the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm (also known as the Damped Least Squares method). We can choose how many points to actually fit. Usually we don't take all 4000 points, but the first 1000 or 2000, because attempting to fit the portion when the polarization has largely decayed will only worsen the fit.⁴ The fit parameters are recorded along with a host of other parameters and data. The most important piece of data is the fit parameter A_1 which gives us the Larmor frequency of the atom. After a pump-probe cycle is finished, the program immediately starts a new one and repeats as needed.

As in CPP mode, we usually run PTP in batches of 20 points each. The

²This was very important in the early stages when we determined the Larmor frequency by averaging a number of traces and then fitting a curve to it using Mathematica.

³We have found that this does not always result in the value read from the pump monitor being exactly zero, and so might investigate setting it to a larger or smaller value in the future.

⁴Later we will discover that slightly altering the number of points to fit will also slightly shift the fitted frequency, which becomes another problem bringing the veracity of the fitted frequency into question, and certainly worthy of deeper investigation.

program then calculates the mean and SD of the fit parameters. There is also an option to save the individual traces for possible later additional data analysis. Usually we only save the decaying portion, as saving complete traces takes up a lot of hard disk space.

Chapter 5

Investigations Using the PTP Scheme

In this chapter, we shall report the results of our investigations using the pump-then-probe scheme, which we shall discuss before CPP because we did the final analysis roughly in this order. All of the measurements are done using the two-cell stack setup described in Ch. 3 and 4, with the “brown dot” cell at the bottom and the “short stem” cell on top. The typical lifetimes were ~ 43 ms for the top cell and ~ 101 ms for the bottom cell.

5.1 Statistical Noise Measurements

The key to probing LRSSIs using our experiment is to monitor changes in the spin precession frequency of the atoms with time. Thus the first task we did was to measure the typical noise level of the frequency measurements over a short period of time and see whether it is small enough to fulfill the sensitivity

goal expressed in Eq. 2.70. As for PTP, $t_{data} \approx 0.6$ s, so we want the standard deviation of the measured frequencies $\sigma_{\nu_{Cs}}$ to be

$$\sigma_{\nu_{Cs}} < 32 \times 10^{-6} \times \sqrt{\frac{6 \times 10^5}{0.6}} = 32 \text{ mHz.} \quad (5.1)$$

To perform the noise level measurement, we run the PTP procedure outlined in Ch. 4 for several minutes. Fig. 5.1 shows how the frequency varies in a data run of 100 points, for both the top and bottom cells. This data, taken on 10 April 2015, was run using the settings shown in Tab. 5.1, which are the standard settings we use to run PTP, including when investigating systematics. The entire set took 60 s to take. The offset is set at 0.020 V as we found that this prevents the pulse amplifier from receiving a negative voltage, which may damage it. While the end value of the pump is set to 0 V, in practice the pump does not turn off completely as the the linear polarizer (No. 7 in Fig. 3.11) has a non-zero extinction ratio.

Parameter	Value
Wave Frequency (Hz)	2135.1
Amplitude (V)	1.0
Offset (V)	0.02
End value (V)	0.0
Duty Cycle (%)	20
Write frequency (Hz)	100000
Read frequency (Hz)	10000
Pump duration (ms)	200
Probe duration (ms)	400
Total pump-probe cycle duration (ms)	600

Table 5.1: Table of settings of various experimental parameters when taking the data of Fig. 5.1.

Figure 5.1: Graphs of a set of standard PTP runs, showing the variation in the fitted frequency over 100 data points, or ~ 1 minute of taking data.

From this, we calculate the mean frequencies

$$\bar{\nu}_{\text{top}} = 2134.482 \text{ Hz}, \quad (5.2)$$

$$\bar{\nu}_{\text{bot}} = 2135.122 \text{ Hz}, \quad (5.3)$$

with the standard deviations

$$\sigma_{\text{top}} = 4.4 \text{ mHz}, \quad (5.4)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{bot}} = 1.8 \text{ mHz}. \quad (5.5)$$

Now, we will be looking at the average frequency between the two Cs cells. The standard deviation of the average frequency between the top and bottom cells, σ_{av} , is

$$\sigma_{\text{av}} = 2.6 \text{ mHz}, \quad (5.6)$$

which is well within the range mandated by Eq. 5.1, so the noise level for PTP is statistically much better than the target sensitivity. When we take the standard deviation of the difference frequency σ_{diff} , we find

$$\sigma_{\text{diff}} = 4.0 \text{ mHz}, \quad (5.7)$$

which is on the same level as Eq. 5.5. This indicates that the noise is not common mode noise, and may come from other sources such as the fitting process (as we will discuss later). This brings us to the next step of investigation, which is testing for systematics.

5.2 PTP Systematics Testing: Overview

The accuracy of an experiment can never be better than the systematic error. The low level of noise in Eq. 5.6 would be futile if it turned out that our frequency could easily vary due to changes in some experimental parameters when taking data. The actual experiment will involve taking data in two table positions, and there is a large risk of things systematically changing due to the table rotation. We investigate this risk by artificially varying several experimental parameters one at a time and seeing how much the frequency varies, resulting in graphs of systematics. We then estimate how much we can keep each experimental parameter constant. We will do this mainly based on our past experience with Gen I. From this, we hope to find a region in the graph where the slope of the measured frequency is small enough so that the total variation in frequency in that region is smaller than the ultimate sensitivity goal of $32 \mu\text{Hz}$ (Eq. 2.68). If we can find such a region and operate our experiment in it, then that particular systematic will not be a problem for us. For the case of some parameters like pump frequency, we have no choice of operating region (as we will have to pump at line center).

The four main parameters that we vary for both PTP and CPP are pump intensity, pump frequency, probe intensity, and probe frequency. For CPP, it is also important to investigate the effects of changing the angle between the pump and probe beams. For PTP, as the pump beam is turned off during the probing, we expect that the measured frequency should be relatively immune to changes due to parameter changes in the pump. Changes to the pump may affect the amplitude of the fit, but the Larmor frequency should stay the

same as we are not affecting the magnetic field. When varying the parameter, we often increased the value up to a point and then decreased it back, to counteract any natural drifts occurring by e.g., thermal fluctuations in the room, which have a time scale of 20-30 minutes, about the time scale needed to take the data.

5.3 Investigating Changes in Pump Intensity

We shall start by investigating the pump intensity. Pump intensity in PTP can be varied in several ways. One can artificially increase the offset, amplitude, or the duty cycle of the wave generated from the DAQ, as all of these effectively decide how much light is “given” to the atom. It is more straightforward, however, to use an attenuator/filter, as we did with the neutral density aluminum-coated attenuator wheel described in Ch. 3.5.5. We collected data for 20 runs, changed the pump intensity by spinning the wheel, waited a few seconds for things to settle down, resumed collecting data for another 20 runs, and so on. The intensity of the pump was measured by taking the last 100 points in the pump monitor before pumping was stopped and finding the peak-to-peak values of the pump modulation by using the Extract Single Tone Information VI in LabVIEW, which uses a fast Fourier transform method to accomplish this. This quantity is proportional to the pump intensity: a lower pump intensity would result in less spin polarization and thus a smaller peak-to-peak amplitude in the pump modulation.

The results are shown in Fig. 5.2. As the intensity is increased, we see

Figure 5.2: Graph of frequency vs. bottom cell pump intensity, taken on April 1-3, 2015. In the top graph, the top cell (red squares) and bottom cell (blue circles) frequencies are plotted on the primary and secondary axes respectively, while the average frequency (yellow triangles) is plotted on the lower graph. Throughout the rest of this thesis we will follow this coloring and marker shape convention.

an increase in the average frequency that peters out starting at $V \approx 0.5$ V. From $V = 0.5 - 0.7$ V, the frequency is stable but has noise in the 10 mHz range. This is likely the stable region that we can operate in. In Fig. 5.3 we fit a straight line to this region, which has the slope of $3(6)$ $\mu\text{Hz}/\text{mV}$. As the uncertainty of the slope is larger than the slope itself, we can regard it as the systematic uncertainty itself. Thus, we have a systematic uncertainty of 6 μHz , or an order of magnitude lower than the ultimate sensitivity goal (32 μHz). Based on this rough assessment, we should not have to worry about changes in pump intensity. However, the data in this stable region is still quite noisy and spotty. Finer and more thorough scans of this region should be done to more properly calculate the slope.

5.4 Investigating Changes in Pump Frequency

We shall now proceed to discuss the systematics test we ran for changes in pump frequency. To vary the pump frequency, we unlock the pump and adjust the bias voltage on the pump laser piezo in small increments. As the pump is unlocked, the noise level is naturally higher. We can calibrate the x -axis to frequency units by observing the error signal from the single phase SR510 lock-in amplifier, which follows the shape shown in Fig. A.2. The horizontal distance between the peak and the valley surrounding the center is given by the full width half maximum of the original absorption curve (Fig. A.1). This

Figure 5.3: Closeup of stable region of frequency vs. pump intensity, showing the fitted straight line, which has the equation $\nu = 0.003(6)I_{\text{pump}} + 2134.016(3)$, where I_{pump} is the pump intensity.

is known as the Doppler width, calculated by the formula

$$\nu_{FWHM} = \sqrt{\frac{8k_bT}{mc^2}}\nu_0, \quad (5.8)$$

where T is the room temperature (~ 300 K), m is the mass of a Cs atom ($\approx 2.21 \times 10^{-25}$ kg), and ν_0 is the frequency of the line center (894 nm), giving us $\nu_{FWHM} \approx 365$ MHz.

The results of our investigation using this calibrated x -axis are shown in Fig. 5.4, which resembles a lopsided dispersion curve. Fig. 5.5 zooms in on the central region near line center and fits a straight line to it. We find the slope to be $0.21(2)$ mHz/MHz. We observe that when the pump is locked using the frequency locking mechanism described in Appendix A, the error signal on the lock-in has noise on the level of ~ 1 unit. Meanwhile, the Doppler width of ~ 365 Hz is ~ 80 units wide, which means the pump frequency varies on the level of ~ 5 MHz. The actual noise in pump frequency during an experiment will be even smaller, because we will be using saturated absorption, which causes a sharp dip at line center in the Cs absorption profile that we lock to. This significantly improves the robustness of the locking mechanism

The actual frequency shift between the two table positions is much smaller than the noise level of the pump. In the Gen I experiment, we typically find the ratio

$$\frac{\Delta\nu_{\text{odd}}}{\Delta\nu_{\text{noise}}} \approx 10^{-3}, \quad (5.9)$$

where $\Delta\nu_{\text{odd}}$ is the table-dependent systematic shift and $\Delta\nu_{\text{noise}}$ is the pump noise level. Assuming Gen II will exhibit similar behavior, we can estimate

Figure 5.4: Graphs of Cs frequency vs. pump frequency from line center, taken on April 1-3, 2015.

Figure 5.5: Closeup of stable region of frequency vs. pump frequency, showing the fitted straight line, which has the equation $\nu = 0.00021(2)\nu_{\text{pump}} + 2133.977(2)$, where ν_{pump} is the pump frequency.

$\Delta\nu_{\text{odd}} \approx 5$ kHz, which will result in a systematic uncertainty of ~ 0.001 mHz, an order of magnitude below the ultimate sensitivity goal. Thus neither the noise nor the systematic frequency shift coming from changes in the pump frequency should be something to worry about.

5.5 Investigating Changes in Probe Intensity

Next, we will report our investigations on changes in probe intensity. Probe intensity is adjusted by rotating the HWP we set up on the optics table before the light is sent to the beam divider (No. 15 in Fig. 3.11). As the probe is shining constantly, we do not expect it to affect the measured frequency by much. The results are shown in Fig. 5.6. The x -axis is the amplitude

of the fit function of the bottom cell (fit parameter A_3 in Eq. 2.62), which correlates well with our adjustments on the HWP and thus is a good proxy of probe intensity. At high intensities, this quantity saturates, but this is not a problem as we normally already operate at near the maximum probe intensity without saturation.¹ As the data is noisy over the entire range of intensities, there is no particular region that is relatively stabler. Hence we fit a straight line to all the points, giving a slope of $0.005(2) \text{ Hz/V} = 5 \mu\text{Hz/mV}$. Assuming again that we can keep the probe laser intensity stable to within $\sim 1 \text{ mV}$, we will get a systematic uncertainty of $5 \mu\text{Hz}$, a factor of 6 better than the sensitivity goal. Thus this systematic should also not be of much concern.

¹The dual lock-ins have an input voltage limit that limits us from operating the probe laser at the fullest intensity.

Figure 5.6: Graphs of Cs frequency vs. bottom cell fit amplitude, which correlates linearly with probe intensity, taken on April 1-3, 2015. The lower graph of average frequency has a fitted straight line with the equation $\nu = 0.0052(2)I_{\text{probe}} + 2134.856(1)$, where I_{probe} is the probe intensity.

5.6 Investigating Changes in Probe Frequency

We will now discuss our investigations on changes in the probe frequency. We adjust the probe frequency in a similar way to the pump frequency, which is by adjusting the bias voltage on the probe cavity piezo. We can use Jeff Lock to track the transmissions peaks as they move, using our knowledge that the free spectral range is ~ 500 MHz to calibrate the measurement. The results are shown in Fig. 5.7. As with the probe intensity, there is no particular region in the graph that is relatively stabler, so we fit a straight line to the entire range. We obtain a slope of $0.010(5)$ mHz/MHz. Now, the robustness of the F-P cavity's locking mechanism is limited by the stability of the He-Ne laser we lock to, which is currently on the order of several MHz (for our homemade laser). Even if we obtained a commercial stabilized He-Ne laser, it would probably not be stabler than ~ 1 MHz. This results in a systematic uncertainty of 0.01 mHz = 10 μ Hz, which is quite close to the sensitivity goal - only a factor of 3 smaller. This is our biggest systematic yet, and it may be require us to be very careful with the probe frequency. A possible proposal for improving the probe frequency would be to lock the probe laser to a laser that is locked to a saturated absorption signal (similar to the pump laser), instead of to a He-Ne laser that is merely thermally stabilized like we have now.

5.7 Investigating the Fitting Process

While so far, we have not found a systematic that is projected to be a problem for our sensitivity goal, we still see variations on the order of ~ 10 mHz on

Figure 5.7: Graphs of Cs frequency vs. probe frequency, taken on April 1-3, 2015. The lower graph of average frequency has a fitted straight line with the equation $\nu = 0.000010(5)\nu_{\text{probe}} + 2134.009(3)$, where ν_{probe} is the probe frequency.

several systematics as we vary them over a large range. For example, in the graphs of frequency vs. pump intensity (Fig. 5.2), we see a variation of ~ 0.04 Hz over the entire range of pump intensity. This is slightly intriguing, as in PTP, the pump is not shining when the atoms are being probed, so whatever the net spin polarization of the system, they should decay while spinning at the same Larmor frequency. We suspected that this shift may have to do with problems with the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm LabVIEW is using to fit the curve. It is possible that the algorithm might have some dependency on the initial amplitude of the decay being fitted. It is also possible that despite having pumped for what we consider an ample amount of time (200 ms) for the atoms to become fully polarized, there are still some small fluctuations in the amplitude. Thus, this will result in small shifts in the fitted frequency even though the actual precession frequency will be the same. Another possibility is that the pump laser is not completely extinguished by the Pockels cell during the probing stage. In this section, we shall report some of the investigations that led us to be aware of potential limitations in the fitting algorithm.

5.7.1 Investigating Changes in Pump Duration

If the system is not fully polarized after 200 ms of pumping, a longer pump time might make it stabler. Thus, if the fitting algorithm is dependent on the initial amplitude as we theorized, we expect the fitted frequency to vary as we vary the pump duration. In fact, we might expect the fitted frequency to stabilize as the pump duration lengthens. So we performed tests where we varied the pump duration specified to the DAQ, from extremely short to over several times the

regular duration. The results are shown in Fig. 5.8. Each point was taken 3-4 times to counteract noise. At extremely short pump durations, as expected, the fitted frequency has a sharp increase. When the $t_{\text{pump}} > 100$ ms, the average frequency flattens out with a noise level of ~ 0.01 Hz. However, if we look at the individual plots of the top and bottom cells, starting at $t_{\text{pump}} = 100$ ms, we see a modulation that is somewhat sinusoidal. This sinusoidal variation seemed to indicate something to do with the algorithm, instead of a physical effect.

As increasing the pump duration even longer would make PTP not feasible, we became curious as to what would happen if we were to try the same investigation, but with double the amplitude of the wave sent out by the DAQ. This effectively increases the overall pump intensity, equivalent to increasing the driving force on the damped harmonic oscillator, hopefully making it stabilize quicker. The results are shown in Fig. 5.9. Looking at the results $t_{\text{pump}} < 100$ ms, the average frequency varies by 0.02 Hz, a factor of 2 better than when the amplitude was 1 V. In the individual plots for the two cells, There is still an up-down pattern but it is less sinusoidal than before. This indicates that it may be better to operate at slightly longer pump durations, if we can afford the time, as the current $t_{\text{pump}} = 200$ ms is just on the verge of the stable region in the graph. We did not attempt even larger amplitudes of the pump, as the pulse amplifier is unable to take amplitudes larger than 2 V.

Figure 5.8: Graphs of Cs frequency vs. pump duration, taken on April 1-3, 2015. The amplitude of the sent wave is 1.0 V, which is the “usual” setting.

Figure 5.9: Graphs of Cs frequency vs. pump duration, taken on April 1-3, 2015. The amplitude of the sent wave is 2.0 V, which is double the “usual” setting.

5.7.2 Investigating Changes in Pump Modulation Frequency

Another parameter we investigated was the pump modulation frequency. To do this, we simply change the setting on the wave sent out to the DAQ. This was done on the maximum amplitude of 2 V, to try to quickly saturate the polarization of the system. The effect of this should be similar to pump duration, in that the closer we get to the Larmor frequency, the fitted frequency should become stabler. The results are shown in Fig. 5.10, and they are surprising as the average frequency graph resembles a dispersion curve in the region of the Larmor frequency. When we do finer increments around the actual Larmor frequency (Fig. 5.11), we can clearly see the fit frequency of the top and bottom cells crisscrossing, meeting at approximately the Larmor frequency. This is a mystery that we are still investigating. What is important, though is to keep the modulation frequency constant, which is not difficult to do with our DAQ.

Figure 5.10: Graphs of Cs frequency vs. pump modulation frequency, taken on April 1-3, 2015. The amplitude of the sent wave is 2.0 V, which is double the “usual” setting.

Figure 5.11: A closeup view near the Larmor frequency of the graphs of Cs frequency vs. pump modulation frequency of Fig. 5.10. We can clearly see the fitted frequency of the top and bottom cells crisscrossing near the Larmor frequency.

5.7.3 Investigating the Number of Points Skipped Before Fitting

Finally, we explore what happens when we vary the initial number of data points we skip in the spin decay signal before starting to fit. This is a direct proxy for varying the initial polarization of the system, as we are effectively waiting for the system to decay first before measuring it. This investigation gave us the most damning evidence of oddities in the fitting algorithm, as opposed to the physics of the system. Fig. 5.12 shows the results. In the upper graph, we can see a clearly non-random sinusoidal trend in the bottom cell fitted frequency, whereas the top cell also has a little bit of sinusoidal modulation but is mostly a linear decrease. In the lower graph of the noise

level (σ) against points skipped, for the bottom cell we also see a sinusoidal variation, although they are all within 1.5-2.0 mHz, which is the typical level for the bottom cell. For the top cell, σ slowly increases from 3 mHz to 4 mHz over a variation of 0-200 points skipped (or 0-20 ms before fitting). This clearly sinusoidal behavior is definitely something to do with the fitting algorithm. Thus, we need to more thoroughly investigate the fitting process before we put our full faith in it. On the other hand, it is perhaps more important to ensure that once we settle on a fitting routine, we stick to its exact settings and parameters for all of our data analysis.

Figure 5.12: Graphs of Cs frequency vs. number of points skipped in the fitting process. Normally we fit starting at $t = 200$ ms, when the pumping stops. Here, each point skipped represents a 0.1 ms delay before fitting a curve to the decay. The data is otherwise taken using “usual” settings (among others, a 1 V pump wave amplitude and $t_{\text{pump}} = 200$ ms).

5.8 Summary

To summarize, we have investigated how changing various parameters in the experiment affects the measured fitted frequency in the PTP scheme. Tab. 5.2 summarizes these findings. In this table, the second column indicates the slope of the systematics response graph in the stable operating region that we have chosen (or the required region, in the case of pump frequency). The third column indicates upper limits on how much the parameter can change, based on our experience with Gen I. The last column shows the resulting systematic uncertainty in the fitted frequency. We can see that there is no systematic that

PTP systematics			
Parameter	Slope	Change limit	Total $\Delta\nu$
Pump intensity	-	-	0.006 mHz
Pump frequency	0.21 mHz/MHz	0.005 MHz	0.001 mHz
Probe intensity	0.005 mHz/mV	1 mV	0.005 mHz
Probe frequency	0.01 mHz/MHz	1 MHz	0.01 mHz

Table 5.2: Summary of PTP systematics. The sensitivity goal is 0.03 mHz. One can see that all the systematic uncertainties are below this level.

causes real concern, assuming we can get the Gen II experimental parameters to behave within the same ballpark (or even better) than Gen I. The most troubling systematic currently is the probe frequency, but even in this case the systematic uncertainty is still a factor of 3 smaller than the sensitivity goal. Of course, Gen II differs in many ways from Gen I, both physical and mechanical. We have not, for example, decided on how we are going to hold the cells and probe detector in place in the rotating table apparatus. Thus this table can only be used as a rough guideline. It is also the case that we still do

not fully understand why changing anything about the pump affects the fitted frequency measurably. As we have seen in Sec. 5.7, there are peculiarities about the fitting algorithm that must be investigated in greater depth if we are to go forward with PTP as a method. Also, finer and more thorough scans of the designated stable operating regions for each parameter must be performed, to better determine the slopes of the graphs.

Chapter 6

Investigations Using the CPP Scheme

In this chapter, we shall report the results of investigations using the continuous pumping-probing (CPP) scheme. Similar to our PTP investigations, we did a basic noise level measurement, then commenced doing systematics investigations in order to decide on how suitable it is for our purposes. The cells used are the same as when investigating PTP: the “brown dot” cell at the bottom and the “short stem cell” on top.

6.1 Statistical Noise Measurements

To measure the basic noise level, we ran the apparatus on CPP for several minutes and measured the noise on the phase of the top and bottom cells using the standard procedure outlined in Ch. 4. Unlike PTP, there are not so many settings when running on CPP. This data set was taken using a Larmor

frequency of 2135.1 Hz, 60 ms integration time, 20% duty cycle, 0.02 V offset (to prevent the signal amplifier from receiving negative voltage), and 1.0 V amplitude. We must note that because for CPP, $t_{\text{data}} = 1.1$ s, which is almost twice that of PTP (mainly due to our efforts to prevent the dual-phase lock-ins from being overloaded with commands), the sensitivity goal is slightly more stringent, namely

$$\sigma_{\nu_{\text{Cs}}} < 32 \times 10^{-6} \times \sqrt{\frac{6 \times 10^5}{1.1}} = 23 \text{ mHz}. \quad (6.1)$$

Fig. 6.1 shows a typical data set from a noise measurement run. In this example, the sensitivities η of the top and bottom were measured out (using the calibration method of Sec. 4.1.2) to be

$$\eta_{\text{top}} = 14 \text{ degrees/Hz}, \quad (6.2)$$

$$\eta_{\text{bot}} = 31 \text{ degrees/Hz}, \quad (6.3)$$

which are typical values for the sensitivity, reflecting the fact that the bottom cell lifetime is roughly twice of the top cell lifetime. To calculate the average frequency ν_{diff} between the two cells, we must scale the phase measurements by these sensitivities, as expressed in the formula

$$\nu_{\text{ave}} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\theta_{\text{top}}}{\eta_{\text{top}}} + \frac{\theta_{\text{bot}}}{\eta_{\text{bot}}} \right). \quad (6.4)$$

The mean absolute value of the phase or frequency of the data set is not important as it is completely arbitrary, depending on when and where we set

Figure 6.1: Graphs of a set of standard CPP runs. The upper graph shows variation in phase over 100 data points, while the lower graph shows variation in the average frequency, calculated using Eq. 6.4. The data was taken on April 10, 2015. The absolute values of the phase and frequency are arbitrary; they were set to zero at the beginning of the measurements.

the zero on the lock-ins. The standard deviation is what we need, and in this case we obtain

$$\sigma_{\text{top}} = \frac{0.0320 \text{ degrees}}{14 \text{ degrees/Hz}} = 2.25 \text{ mHz} \quad (6.5)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{bot}} = \frac{0.0698 \text{ degrees}}{31 \text{ degrees/Hz}} = 2.22 \text{ mHz}, \quad (6.6)$$

and from the set of average frequencies we obtain

$$\sigma_{\text{ave}} = 2.2 \text{ mHz}, \quad (6.7)$$

only slightly better than that obtained by PTP (see. Eq. 5.6), and an order of magnitude better than the limit in Eq. 6.1. One feature we noticed was that the two cells tracked each other nicely. When we took the frequency difference between the cells, i.e.

$$\nu_{\text{diff}} = \left(\frac{\theta_{\text{top}}}{\eta_{\text{top}}} - \frac{\theta_{\text{bot}}}{\eta_{\text{bot}}} \right), \quad (6.8)$$

the noise level was significantly reduced, as shown in Fig. 6.2; we obtained

$$\sigma_{\text{ave}} = 0.3 \text{ mHz}, \quad (6.9)$$

an order of magnitude smaller than σ_{ave} . This indicates that the noise we see is common mode noise. We do not know yet whether this common mode noise is magnetic field noise or laser noise. If it is magnetic field noise, then when we take the difference between the the Cs and Hg frequencies (Eq. 2.12) in

the actual experiment, it will also be canceled out, leading to a similar order of magnitude improvement on the sensitivity. On the other hand, if it is laser noise, then as the Hg cell will be pumped using a different laser, this will not be canceled out when taking the frequency difference between Cs and Hg. Thus it is important in the future to further investigate what the source of the noise is, as this might be an additional advantage for the CPP method. In the case of PTP, we did not see this common mode noise.

Thus while based on our initial noise measurement the CPP scheme seems to be on the same level as PTP, there are several systematics tests which need to be done before we can decide on its robustness as a whole. This we shall discuss in the next sections.

Figure 6.2: Graphs of the difference frequency of a set of standard CPP runs, showing the variation in frequency over 100 data points, taken on April 10, 2015. The difference frequency is calculated using Eq. 6.8.

6.2 CPP Systematics Testing: Overview

The main systematics tests we will run on the CPP scheme will be similar to PTP, in that we will vary the pump intensity, pump frequency, probe intensity, and probe frequency. We will see if there are any stable operating regions that give a frequency shift of less than the ultimate sensitivity goal of $32 \mu\text{Hz}$. CPP differs from PTP, however, in that in addition to these, we have to pay attention to the angle between the pump and probe lasers. This is because even a slight misalignment will cause a phase shift between the pump and probe, which is the quantity we are measuring. This is the greatest risk for the CPP method. Another risk is because the pump is always on, we expect varying parameters on the pump will affect the measurement. We do not, however, have to worry about the duration of the pump or any fitting algorithms.

For all of the following investigations, we use the same settings as when doing the noise measurement of Sec. 6.1. We measured the sensitivity η of the cells each time and always found them to be approximately equal to the values in Eq. 6.3. The y -axis values of the graphs displayed were originally phase measured in degrees, which we divided by the relevant η to result in units of frequency (Hz) that we can compare with PTP values. We are concerned with the variation in these frequency values, as the absolute value of the phase or frequency is meaningless (as opposed to PTP, where the absolute value of the measured frequency is really the Larmor frequency).

6.3 Investigating Changes in Pump Intensity

We start our systematics investigations by varying the pump intensity. This was performed using the same method as with PTP, which is by rotating the neutral density filter wheel. The pump intensity was measured by reading it off the pump monitor channel as displayed on a digital oscilloscope that gave us the peak-to-peak values of the signal. The results are shown in Fig. 6.3. Over a wide range of pump intensity (from maximum to almost zero), we see that for the top and bottom cells, starting from low intensity the frequency decreases sharply until it hits a turning point at $V \approx 0.5V$, after which it increases gradually.

Figure 6.3: Graph of Cs phase vs. pump intensity, taken on April 13, 2015. The y -axis values have been divided by the sensitivity η for each cell. The x -axis values are the peak-to-peak value of the bottom pump monitor.

In Fig. 6.4 we focus on the flat turning point region from $V \approx 0.4 - 0.9$ V and fit a straight line to it. We find a slope of 0.01 (1) mHz/mV, which is

admittedly a large uncertainty in the fit. From on our experience with Gen I, the pump intensity can be kept constant to a part per 1000 (see Appendix C for data and details on this value), which is ~ 1 mV as DC intensity is about a volt. Thus the systematic uncertainty will be 0.01 mHz, which is only a factor of 3 smaller than the sensitivity goal. This may be a cause for concern, but more data needs to be taken in this stable region to more accurately determine the value of the slope.

Figure 6.4: Closeup of stable region of frequency vs. pump intensity, showing the fitted straight line, which has the equation $\nu = 0.01(1)I_{\text{pump}} - 0.046(9)$, where I_{pump} is the pump intensity.

6.4 Investigating Changes in Pump Frequency

We shall now discuss changes in the pump frequency. As with PTP, we varied the pump frequency by varying the bias voltage on the piezo of the pump laser.

This corresponded to a range of ~ 1500 MHz variation. We were able to vary the frequency over a wider range than PTP as the signal quality decreased more slowly. The results of this investigation are shown in Fig. 6.5. We calibrated the x -axis using the same method as we did in Sec. 5.4 by using the Doppler-broadened width. The region around the line center is examined in Fig. 6.6. We find a slope of $0.31(4)$ mHz/MHz. Now assume as we did in the PTP investigations of pump frequency that the systematic uncertainty is ~ 5 kHz. This would correspond to a noise of 0.002 mHz, an order of magnitude below the sensitivity goal. Thus pump frequency is not a systematic that causes concern.

Figure 6.5: Graph of Cs phase vs. pump frequency, taken on April 13, 2015. The y -axis values have been divided by the sensitivity η for each cell. The x -axis is the frequency difference to the line center (which is set to be 0).

Figure 6.6: Closeup of stable region of frequency vs. pump frequency, showing the fitted straight line, which has the equation $\nu = -0.00031(4)\nu_{\text{pump}} + 0.011(5)$, where ν_{pump} is the pump frequency.

6.5 Investigating Changes in Probe Intensity

We report the results of investigating changes in probe intensity. Using the same method as with PTP, we rotated the HWP before the beam divider in the path of the probe laser in order to vary the intensity of the probe. In the PTP investigation, the fitted amplitude was used as a proxy for probe intensity. This time, the intensity is measured by applying the same LabVIEW Extract Single Tone Information VI to the signal on the DIFF channel of the probe photodetector for the bottom cell. The results are shown in Fig. 6.7. The shape of the graph in the low intensity region is similar to that of pump intensity (Fig. 6.3) in that there is a decreasing graph with a slope approaching zero, but unlike pump intensity, the probe intensity graph does not have a full turning point, but merely relaxes in slope in the decrease. In Fig. 6.4, we

focus on this stable region of $V > 0.4$ V. We find a slope of 0.04 mHz/mV. Assuming as before that we can keep the laser intensities to within a part per thousand (1 mV), we obtain a systematic uncertainty of 0.04 mHz. This is slightly higher than the sensitivity goal (0.03 mHz), and so if we are to use CPP, this is a systematic we will have to improve on. However, since we are in the right ballpark (in orders of magnitude), this should be possible.

Figure 6.7: Graph of Cs phase vs. probe intensity, taken on April 13, 2015. The y -axis values have been divided by the sensitivity η for each cell. The x -axis values are the average of the reading on the bottom DIFF channel (calculated using a LabVIEW FFT algorithm).

6.6 Investigating Changes in Probe Frequency

We shall now discuss the results of our investigations into changes in the probe frequency. We used the same method of varying probe frequency as in PTP, which is varying the bias voltage on the piezo of the probe laser cavity and

Figure 6.8: Closeup of stable region of frequency vs. probe intensity, showing the fitted straight line, which has the equation $\nu = -0.04(4)I_{\text{probe}} + 0.01(2)$, where ν_{pump} is the pump intensity.

tracking the amount of change on the Jeff Lock LabVIEW program. We varied the probe over a 300 MHz frequency range, as we did for PTP. The results are shown in Fig. 6.9. As when we did it for PTP, the frequency varies noisily without any particular region being relatively stabler than others. So we fitted a straight line to the average frequency over the entire range, which gives us a slope of 0.05(1) mHz/MHz. Assuming as we did earlier that the He-Ne laser of the F-P cavity cannot be stabler than 1 MHz, this gives a systematic uncertainty of 0.05 mHz, higher than the sensitivity goal. Like the case with the probe intensity, this uncertainty is still within the right ballpark,

Figure 6.9: Graph of frequency vs. probe frequency, taken on April 13, 2015. The y -axis values have been divided by the sensitivity η for each cell. The x -axis values are the relative position of one of the probe laser transmission peaks on the F-P cavity, as recorded by the LabVIEW program Jeff Lock. The straight line fitted to the average frequency plot has the equation $\nu = -0.00005(1)\nu_{\text{probe}} - 0.309(6)$, where ν_{probe} is the probe frequency.

6.7 Investigating Changes in Pump-Probe Angle

As has been mentioned in Sec. 6.2, for CPP it is important for the angle between the pump and probe lasers, which are supposed to be orthogonal, to be kept as constant as possible. There is a great risk of the lasers shifting as the table rotates between the two positions. Based on our experience with Gen I, we estimate that the laser beams will move with a total displacement standard deviation of $\sigma_{tot} = 0.4$ millidegrees (see Appendix C for a fuller explanation on how we derived this value, including some data plots from Gen I). Converting this to frequency units using the cell sensitivities in Eq. 6.3, we get a variation of

$$\Delta\nu_{top} = 0.02 \text{ mHz}, \quad (6.10)$$

$$\Delta\nu_{bot} = 0.01 \text{ mHz}, \quad (6.11)$$

which is only slightly lower than the sensitivity goal. Thus if we want to use CPP, we must make special efforts to keep this parameter under control.

6.8 Summary

Having investigated the phase response to the changing of various parameters in the experiment using the CPP scheme, we summarize them in Tab. 6.1. As we have seen, overall CPP performs worse than PTP in all systematics, which is not surprising as in this scheme the pump is always on, so changes to it will

more easily affect the rest of the experiment. However, all of the systematic uncertainties are still either below or around the order of magnitude of the ultimate sensitivity goal of $32 \mu\text{Hz}$. This means that it is still realistic to go forward with CPP as a method, although we would have to make special efforts to slightly suppress the systematics below the sensitivity goal. One reason why we might want to do this is if the common mode noise between the two cells (Sec. 6.1) turns out to be magnetic noise, then CPP might possibly have an order of magnitude advantage over PTP when we are working with both Cs and Hg cells. This is because we would be taking the difference between Hg and Cs frequencies. However, at this current point CPP is not as promising as PTP.

CPP systematics			
Parameter	Slope	Change limit	Total $\Delta\nu$
Pump intensity	0.01 mHz/mV	1 mV	0.01 mHz
Pump frequency	0.31 mHz/MHz	0.005 MHz	0.002 mHz
Probe intensity	0.04 mHz/mV	1 mV	0.04 mHz
Probe frequency	0.05 mHz/MHz	1 MHz	0.05 mHz

Table 6.1: Summary of CPP systematics. The sensitivity goal is 0.03 mHz. One can see that all the systematic uncertainties are below or around this level.

Chapter 7

Conclusions and Future Outlook

We have finished describing the theoretical motivations of our experiment, the physics behind it, and the physical details of the apparatus. We have also reported the current results of our ongoing investigation into systematic effects. In this chapter, we shall summarize all of these findings and also take a brief look at the future plans for the Gen II experiment.

7.1 Summary of Findings

We have explored the systematic effects of changing pump intensity, pump frequency, probe intensity, and probe frequency on the Larmore frequency being measured on both the PTP and CPP schemes. We have also dealt with some peculiar features of each scheme (the fitting process in PTP, and pump-probe alignment in CPP). Tab. 7.1 summarizes the findings, comparing PTP and CPP directly. PTP clearly has roughly an order of magnitude advantage in the systematic uncertainties compared to CPP. As the statistical noise level of

the average frequencies of both methods are about the same, at this point PTP seems to be a more promising approach. However, as we have mentioned, it remains to be determined whether the common mode noise in CPP is magnetic field noise, laser noise, or some other unknown source. If it is magnetic noise, then this will be an advantage when we take the difference frequencies between Cs and Hg in the actual experiment. Still, even if this turned out to be true, we will still be limited by the large systematic uncertainties in CPP, so unless we come up with improvements that dramatically improve the stability of each parameter compared to Gen I, CPP does not seem to be a feasible scheme.

Summary of Systematics		
Parameter	Total $\Delta\nu$, PTP (mHz)	Total $\Delta\nu$, CPP (mHz)
Pump intensity	0.006	0.01
Pump frequency	0.001	0.002
Probe intensity	0.005	0.04
Probe frequency	0.01	0.05

Table 7.1: Overall Summary of Systematic Uncertainties for PTP and CPP schemes. The ultimate sensitivity goal is 0.03 mHz.

7.2 Future Outlook

Based on the findings in Sec. 7.1, it seems that the PTP method is more optimal for our future tracking of the Cs frequency. The next step is to solidify these findings further by doing finer variations on each of the parameters on the PTP scheme, as we have mentioned in the discussions on systematic uncertainties. Secondly, we should try to find out the source of the common mode noise for CPP, which may predict how well we will do when doing frequency

subtraction with the Hg cell.

Next, we should investigate our fitting process for PTP more thoroughly. Even if we cannot make the fitting algorithm give a stable result when varying some of its parameters, we should decide on what settings to use and stick to them for the rest of the experiment. Additionally, we might also consider replacing the Pockels cell with an Acousto-optic Modulator (AOM) that will extinguish the pump light better during the optical probing stage of PTP. As we have briefly mentioned in Sec. 5.7, this is another possibility for why PTP is currently vulnerable to changes in pumping parameters.

Another task to be done in the near future is to open up the cans and reverse the top and bottom cells to see if their lifetimes remain the same, in order to resolve the mystery reported in Sec. 3.2.3, where the lifetime of the “short stem” cell dropped by a factor of 2 from ~ 90 ms to the current value of 43 ms.

After completing all of these investigations on cesium, we have to do similar experiments on the mercury cells. We anticipate receiving the new Hg cells in the next few months. For Hg, we only have one laser, and it would be cost-prohibitive to purchase another one, so the CPP geometry is out of the question. The only way to track the Hg Larmor frequency would be to pump and probe using the same laser, using a scheme similar to PTP. The laser would first pump for a set time, modulated at the Larmor frequency of Hg. Then it would immediately be shifted 3 GHz away from resonance for probing. With the Cs lasers, we normally have to manually adjust the laser current when changing the bias voltage to detune from resonance. The Hg ultraviolet laser,

however, has a feature in its electronics that should be able to automatically adjust the laser when the bias voltage increases by a large amount.

We tried using this single laser PTP scheme in the early stages of the thesis (May-June 2014) with little success as the lifetimes of the Cs cells are so short (tens of milliseconds). Thus there was not enough time to detune the laser several GHz off resonance for probing, and we were stuck at probing at resonance, which was unsuccessful and led to adoption of the current two-laser geometry. With Hg, however, a typical lifetime is ~ 4 s. Hopefully, this makes such a scheme much easier to realize.

After doing systematics testing on the Hg, we would start designing and building the components needed to fit our new Gen II geometry on the rotating table apparatus. While we will probably be able to reuse the rotating table and magnetic shields from Gen I, we will still have to think about how to mount the probe detectors and the cells, as well as how to monitor the pump. Only then would we finally be able to take data for Gen II, apply our geophysical method and obtain newly improved bounds for LRSSIs.

Appendix A

Principles of Lock-In Amplifiers

In this appendix, we shall elaborate in more detail about the laser frequency locking scheme in our system. The following explanation was mainly adapted from [56] and [76].

A.1 Basic Locking Scheme

As mentioned in Sec. 3.4.2, the locking mechanism relies on the absorption spectrum of the atoms, in this case Cs. Using a beamsplitter, a portion of the light from the ECDL is taken away from the main beam and shone through the reference cell before being fed into a photodiode circuit connected to an oscilloscope. We get an absorption spectrum such as that in Fig. A.1 whenever we pass by the resonant frequency of a transition. The spectrum displays a rather broad, U-shaped dip with the resonant frequency at the line center. This broadening of the dip is a result of the Doppler effect, where atoms that happen to be moving towards the laser beam see a higher frequency and those moving

away see a lower frequency - resulting in absorption even if the frequency is not precisely at the center. Ideally, we would like to lock the frequency to the line center of the dip. We need a feedback mechanism which changes linearly in the region of resonance and gives a value of zero when we are precisely on line center of the resonance. For small departures from resonance, the derivative of the absorption spectrum can provide a good locking voltage (Fig. A.2). We extract this feedback signal using a lock-in amplifier.

Figure A.1: Rough plot of absorption spectrum (V_{absp}) obtained by shining our 894 nm ECDL through the Cs reference cell. Adapted from [56].

A.2 Lock-In Amplifiers in Frequency Locking

In this section, we shall go over the basics of the operation of lock-in amplifiers. Lock-in amplifiers are also used for extracting our signal in the CPP scheme, so this section has relevance beyond just understanding the frequency locking

mechanism.

A lock-in amplifier extracts the amplitude and phase of a signal at a particular *reference frequency*. So, if the signal is constant (DC), one must find a way to modulate it. In our case, we have a Tektronix CFG250 function generator connected to the piezo voltage of the ECDL, which provides a $\sim 5\text{-}10$ kHz modulation about the laser's center frequency. The wave from the function generator is also sent to the lock-in as the reference frequency. Thus, the signal from the photodiode circuit V_{absp} will have the form

$$V_{\text{absp}} = kV_{\text{sig}} \sin(\omega_r t + \theta_{\text{sig}}), \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where k is an arbitrary constant, V_{sig} is the amplitude of the signal modulation set by the function generator, ω_r is the reference frequency, t is time, and θ_{sig} is the phase of the signal. Similarly, the input from the reference frequency signal V_{ref} will have the form

$$V_{\text{ref}} = V_L \sin(\omega_r t + \theta_{\text{ref}}), \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where V_L is the amplitude (which we usually set ~ 0.2 V) and θ_{ref} is the phase of the reference frequency.

The lock-in amplifier then multiplies V_{absp} and V_{ref} , resulting in the convolved signal [76]

$$\begin{aligned} V_{\text{PSD}} &= kV_{\text{sig}}V_L \sin(\omega_r t + \theta_{\text{sig}}) \sin(\omega_r t + \theta_{\text{ref}}) \\ &= \frac{k}{2} V_{\text{sig}}V_L \cos([\omega_r - \omega_r]t + \theta_{\text{sig}} - \theta_{\text{ref}}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\frac{k}{2}V_{\text{sig}}V_L \cos([\omega_r + \omega_r]t + \theta_{\text{sig}} + \theta_{\text{ref}}) \\
& = \frac{k}{2}V_{\text{sig}}V_L \cos(\theta_{\text{sig}} - \theta_{\text{ref}}) \\
& -\frac{k}{2}V_{\text{sig}}V_L \cos(2\omega_r t + \theta_{\text{sig}} + \theta_{\text{ref}}). \tag{A.3}
\end{aligned}$$

The lock-in runs V_{PSD} through a low-pass filter that removes the oscillating (AC) second term in Eq. A.3, leaving us with just the first term, which is the constant DC signal

$$V_{\text{PSD}} = \frac{k}{2}V_{\text{sig}}V_L \cos(\theta_{\text{sig}} - \theta_{\text{ref}}), \tag{A.4}$$

which is the output we read from the lock-in. Now if the amplitude of the modulation, V_{sig} , is small compared to V_{absp} , then the resultant signal will be the derivative of V_{absp} , which is asymmetrical about the y -axis and thus can be used as an error signal to correct any deviations from the line center of the absorption dip (Fig. A.2). We use single-phase Stanford SR510 lock in amplifiers do all of these tasks.

In the past, we have also further enhanced the locking mechanism by creating saturated absorption on the reference cell, such that besides the Doppler-broadened dip of Fig. A.1, a sharp, V-shaped dip appears at the line center. However, this requires two laser beams, which would divert more power away from the main experimental beam. We quickly realized that the locking was robust enough with normal absorption, so we could afford to devote more power for the main beam, giving us more parameter room to work with in the main experiment.

The above method of locking is only applied to the pump laser. For the probe laser, since we tune it ~ 3 GHz away from the line center, the surrounding region of the absorption spectrum is flat and so we cannot utilize the derivative of the absorption profile to lock as we do with the pump. Instead, we use a separate Fabry-Perot cavity to lock the probe laser, of which more will be discussed in Section 3.7.

Figure A.2: Rough plot of the derivative of the absorption spectrum ($dV_{\text{absp}}/d\nu$). Adapted from [56].

Appendix B

Basic Running Procedure

In this appendix we shall discuss in more detail the general settings we normally use when operating our apparatus.

The first thing we do daily is to turn on both the pump and probe lasers, and adjust the current for each so that it is at the setting that corresponds with roughly where the relevant atomic transitions are: for the pump, it is the $6^2S_{1/2}(F = 3) \rightarrow 6^2P_{1/2}(F' = 4)$ transition, whereas for the probe it is the $6^2S_{1/2}(F = 4) \rightarrow 6^2P_{1/2}(F' = 3)$. Using the reference cells, we then do adjust the bias voltage on the piezos using a simple electronics box so that the lasers are on the line center of the absorption profile. We let the lasers stabilize for an hour or so.

We then apply a small amplitude, ~ 400 Hz modulation to the pump laser using the Tektronix CFG250 function generator. The lock function is then turned on, and the pump is locked. For the probe, we take note of the starting position of an F-P transmission peak of the laser on the Jeff Lock program.

We then start increasing the bias voltage on the piezo while observing the movement of the transmission peaks on Jeff Lock. We keep increasing the voltage until we have seen 6 successive transmission peaks pass through. As we do this, we have to sometimes decrease the current to prevent the laser from going multi-mode.¹ Now, as the FSR of the F-P is ~ 500 Hz, this means that we have effectively tuned roughly 3 GHz away from line resonance center.

The figure of 3 GHz was chosen because in our early investigations, tuning further away only further decreased the signal without increasing the lifetime. At the current stage of the experiment, it is not important that we tune precisely to the same position every day, because small deviations in the probe frequency do not affect the system's behavior in a significant way, as long as we are within a few hundred MHz from the 3 GHz detuning.² Another important question is why we increase the voltage, effectively tuning it 3 GHz to the left of the Cs absorption profile of Fig. 2.4, such that the laser is somewhere between the $F = 3 \rightarrow F = 3$ and $F = 4 \rightarrow F = 4$ transitions. The answer is that we did try tuning the other way when doing the lifetime measurements, and found that for some reason the signal-to-noise ratio was slightly better when tuning to the left.

Lastly, we have also briefly investigated different combinations of Cs transitions on the pump and probe. We tried all 16 different combinations using the

¹If we do not do this, then the laser will eventually mode hop back to the original frequency.

²As we discuss in Chs. 5 and 6, the actual *frequency* can indeed change a little bit as the probe frequency deviates. So it is important to keep the probe frequency stable within a single series of runs that are meant to be used to analyze a single property of the system. But it is not as important to keep it stable over several series of runs that aim to investigate different things.

4 hyperfine levels. At that point, we had not started tuning the probe away from resonance, and so the probe was also tuned at or near the line center. In this configuration, only a few combinations worked at all; the results were much better when the two lasers were at different transitions. It was then determined that the current setup of pump at $F = 3 \rightarrow F' = 4$ and probe at $F = 4 \rightarrow F' = 3$ gave the best results. As we now regularly tune the probe 3 GHz away instead of putting it at line center, the initial transition of the probe does not matter as much.

After locking the pump laser, we turn on the He-Ne laser, wait about an hour for it to warm up and stabilize, then activate its locking function that locks the ratio of axial and transverse modes of polarizations, effectively locking the cavity length. Jeff Lock is thus ready to lock the probe laser. In reality, the probe laser is quite stable as is without being locked, especially within the time scales we are investigating at (only 30 minutes at most). Thus often we do not bother to activate Jeff Lock's locking function at all.

Once the locking is done, we turn on the signal amplifier that converts modulation of a few volts to the several hundred volts needed for the Pockels Cell. We also turn on the high voltage power supply from which it draws power, setting it to a maximum of 350 V. The power supply for the magnetic field coils are also turned on to the standard voltage of $V_{\text{base}} = 9.74$ V. We turn on the power supply for the probe photodetectors. We are then ready to operate within one of the two possible data collection schemes: PTP or CPP. These schemes are described in Ch. 4.

Appendix C

Beam Movement and Laser Intensity Variation in Gen I

In this Appendix, we will explain further our method of estimating the amount of variation in beam movement and laser intensity in Gen I, which are useful as rough guides on the future behavior of Gen II.

C.1 Beam Movement

First, we shall discuss our method to estimate how much the laser beam can move as we switch back and forth between the two table positions. In the Gen I apparatus, a fiber bundle was positioned at the top of the cans pointing downwards (see Fig. 2.9) to collect the light from the laser after passing through the vapor cells. The fiber bundle was divided into 4 quadrants which went into 4 separate photodiodes, numbered in clockwise order DC_1 to DC_4 .

We monitored the quadrant asymmetry, as expressed in the quantities

$$Asym_V = \frac{(DC_1 + DC_3) - (DC_2 + DC_4)}{(DC_1 + DC_3) + (DC_2 + DC_4)}, \quad (C.1)$$

which tracked vertical adjustments, and

$$Asym_H = \frac{(DC_1 + DC_4) - (DC_2 + DC_3)}{(DC_1 + DC_4) + (DC_2 + DC_3)} \quad (C.2)$$

which tracked horizontal adjustments. Fig. C.1 shows the change in $Asym_V$ and $Asym_H$, and the total displacement $Assym_{Tot} = \sqrt{Asym_V^2 + Asym_H^2}$ as the table is rotated between the two positions over a series of 12 data runs which were analyzed in the last Gen I paper [47]. The y -axis has been converted into units of millidegrees by calibrating the apparatus using a micrometer attached to one of the mirrors that reflected the beam upwards through the cells. From this data, we calculate the standard deviation of the total displacement $\sigma_{tot} = 0.4$ millidegrees. Converting this to frequency units using the cell sensitivities in Eq. 6.3, we get a variation of

$$\Delta\nu_{top} = 0.02 \text{ mHz}, \quad (C.3)$$

$$\Delta\nu_{bot} = 0.01 \text{ mHz}, \quad (C.4)$$

which are the values cited in Eq. 6.11.

Figure C.1: Graph of Gen I beam movement between two table positions. These were the 12 sets of data taken within the course of a year [47].

C.2 Laser Intensity

Laser intensity variation was estimated by tracking the sums of the absolute values of the voltages on each of the four quadrants of the fiber bundle. The upper graph of Fig. C.2 shows how the total sum varies over 12 data runs, while in the lower graph shows the variation in the difference of the sums between the two table positions over the 12 data runs. The average of the sums is 0.207 V, while the average of the differences is $0.000332 \text{ V} = 0.033 \text{ mV}$. This leads to our estimate that the table-dependent shift in the laser intensity should be around a part per thousand.

Figure C.2: Graph of Gen I beam movement between two table positions. These were the 12 sets of data taken within the course of a year [47].

Bibliography

- [1] Hunter, L., Gordon, J., Peck, S., Ang, D. & Lin, J.-F. Using the earth as a polarized electron source to search for long-range spin-spin interactions. *Science* **339**, 928–932 (2013).
- [2] Hunter, L. & Ang, D. Using geoelectrons to search for velocity-dependent spin-spin interactions. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **112**, 091803 (2014).
- [3] Griffiths, D. *Introduction to Electrodynamics*. Always learning (Pearson, 2013).
- [4] Einstein, A. Zur Elektrodynamik bewegter Körper. *Annalen der Physik* **322**, 891–921 (1905).
- [5] Einstein, A. Über einen die Erzeugung und Verwandlung des Lichtes betreffenden heuristischen Gesichtspunkt. *Annalen der Physik* **322**, 132–148 (1905).
- [6] Einstein, A. Über den Einfluß der Schwerkraft auf die Ausbreitung des Lichtes. *Annalen der Physik* **340**, 898–908 (1911).
- [7] Kragh, H. *Quantum Generations: A History of Physics in the Twentieth*

- Century*. History and philosophy of science (Princeton University Press, 2002).
- [8] Hanneke, D., Fogwell, S. & Gabrielse, G. New measurement of the electron magnetic moment and the fine structure constant. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **100**, 120801 (2008).
- [9] Glashow, S. L. Partial-symmetries of weak interactions. *Nuclear Physics A* **22**, 579–588 (1961).
- [10] Weinberg, S. A Model of Leptons. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **19**, 1264–1266 (1967).
- [11] Griffiths, D. *Introduction to Elementary Particles*. Physics textbook (Wiley, 2008).
- [12] Aubert, J.-J. *et al.* Experimental observation of a heavy particle J . *Physical Review Letters* **33**, 1404 (1974).
- [13] Augustin, J.-E. *et al.* Discovery of a narrow resonance in e^+e^- annihilation. *Physical Review Letters* **33**, 1406 (1974).
- [14] Fritzsche, H. The History of QCD (2012). [Online at <http://cerncourier.com/cws/article/cern/50796>; accessed 26 January 2015].
- [15] Chatrchyan, S. *et al.* Observation of a new boson at a mass of 125 GeV with the CMS experiment at the LHC. *Physics Letters B* **716**, 30–61 (2012). 1207.7235.

- [16] Aad, G. *et al.* Observation of a new particle in the search for the Standard Model Higgs boson with the ATLAS detector at the LHC. *Physics Letters B* **716**, 1–29 (2012). 1207.7214.
- [17] Zwiebach, B. *A First Course in String Theory* (Cambridge University Press, 2009).
- [18] Lee, T. D. & Yang, C. N. Question of parity conservation in weak interactions. *Phys. Rev.* **104**, 254–258 (1956).
- [19] Wu, C. S., Ambler, E., Hayward, R. W., Hoppes, D. D. & Hudson, R. P. Experimental test of parity conservation in beta decay. *Phys. Rev.* **105**, 1413–1415 (1957).
- [20] Christenson, J. H., Cronin, J. W., Fitch, V. L. & Turlay, R. Evidence for the 2π decay of the k_2^0 meson. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **13**, 138–140 (1964).
- [21] Jaeckel, J. & Ringwald, A. The Low-Energy Frontier of Particle Physics. In Holstein, BR and Haxton, WC and Jawahery, A (ed.) *ANNUAL REVIEW OF NUCLEAR AND PARTICLE SCIENCE, VOL 60*, vol. 60 of *Annual Review of Nuclear and Particle Science*, 405–437 (ANNUAL REVIEWS, 2010).
- [22] Amsler, C. *et al.* Review of particle physics. *Physics Letters B* **667**, 1 – 6 (2008). Review of Particle Physics.
- [23] Peccei, R. D. & Quinn, H. R. CP conservation in the presence of pseudoparticles. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **38**, 1440–1443 (1977).

- [24] Moody, J. E. & Wilczek, F. New macroscopic forces? *Phys. Rev. D* **30**, 130–138 (1984).
- [25] Youdin, A. N., Krause, D., Jr., Jagannathan, K., Hunter, L. R. & Lamoreaux, S. K. Limits on spin-mass couplings within the axion window. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **77**, 2170–2173 (1996).
- [26] Ni, W.-T., Pan, S.-s., Yeh, H.-C., Hou, L.-S. & Wan, J. Search for an axionlike spin coupling using a paramagnetic salt with a dc squid. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **82**, 2439–2442 (1999).
- [27] Phillips, D. F. *et al.* Limit on lorentz and CPT violation of the proton using a hydrogen maser. *Phys. Rev. D* **63**, 111101 (2001).
- [28] Nakamura, K. & Group, P. D. Review of particle physics. *Journal of Physics G: Nuclear and Particle Physics* **37**, 075021 (2010).
- [29] Dobrescu, B. A. & Mocioiu, I. Spin-dependent macroscopic forces from new particle exchange. *Journal of High Energy Physics* **2006**, 005 (2006).
- [30] Essig, R. *et al.* Working Group Report: New Light Weakly Coupled Particles (2013). 1311.0029.
- [31] Davoudiasl, H., Lee, H.-S. & Marciano, W. J. 'Dark' Z implications for Parity Violation, Rare Meson Decays, and Higgs Physics. *Phys.Rev.* **D85**, 115019 (2012). 1203.2947.
- [32] Bjorken, J. D. *et al.* Search for neutral metastable penetrating particles produced in the slac beam dump. *Phys. Rev. D* **38**, 3375–3386 (1988).

- [33] Andreas, S., Niebuhr, C. & Ringwald, A. New limits on hidden photons from past electron beam dumps. *Phys. Rev. D* **86**, 095019 (2012).
- [34] Dobrescu, B. A. Massless gauge bosons other than the photon. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **94**, 151802 (2005).
- [35] Georgi, H. Unparticle physics. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **98**, 221601 (2007).
- [36] Liao, Y. & Liu, J.-Y. Long-range electron spin-spin interactions from unparticle exchange. *Physical review letters* **99**, 191804 (2007).
- [37] Neville, D. E. Experimental bounds on the coupling of massless spin-1 torsion. *Phys. Rev. D* **25**, 573–576 (1982).
- [38] Hewett, J. L. & Rizzo, T. G. Low-energy phenomenology of superstring-inspired {E6} models. *Physics Reports* **183**, 193 – 381 (1989).
- [39] Wang, L. & Han, X.-F. Rare z-decay into light pseudoscalar bosons in the simplest little higgs model. *Nuclear Physics B* **853**, 625–634 (2011).
- [40] Hill, C. T. Topcolor assisted technicolor. *Physics Letters B* **345**, 483 – 489 (1995).
- [41] Rizzo, T. G. Z-prime bosons and Kaluza-Klein excitations at muon colliders. *AIP Conf.Proc.* **542**, 152–159 (2000). [hep-ph/0001140](#).
- [42] Heckel, B. R., Adelberger, E. G., Gundlach, J. H., Harris, M. G. & Swanson, H. E. Torsion balance test of spin coupled forces. In *Quantum Gravity, Generalized Theory of Gravitation, and Superstring Theory-Based Unification*, 153–160 (Springer, 2002).

- [43] Vasilakis, G., Brown, J. M., Kornack, T. W. & Romalis, M. V. Limits on new long range nuclear spin-dependent forces set with a \mathbf{K} - ^3He comagnetometer. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **103**, 261801 (2009).
- [44] Hou, L.-S., Ni, W.-T. & Li, Y.-C. M. Test of cosmic spatial isotropy for polarized electrons using a rotatable torsion balance. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **90**, 201101 (2003).
- [45] Brown, J. M., Smullin, S. J., Kornack, T. W. & Romalis, M. V. New limit on lorentz- and *cpt*-violating neutron spin interactions. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **105**, 151604 (2010).
- [46] Heckel, B. R. *et al.* Preferred-frame and *cp*-violation tests with polarized electrons. *Phys. Rev. D* **78**, 092006 (2008).
- [47] Peck, S. *et al.* Limits on local lorentz invariance in mercury and cesium. *Physical Review A* **86**, 012109 (2012).
- [48] Venema, B. J., Majumder, P. K., Lamoreaux, S. K., Heckel, B. R. & Fortson, E. N. Search for a coupling of the earth's gravitational field to nuclear spins in atomic mercury. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **68**, 135–138 (1992).
- [49] Maus, S. *et al.* The us/uk world magnetic model for 2010-2015 (2010).
- [50] Poirier, J. *Introduction to the Physics of the Earth's Interior* (Cambridge University Press, 2000).
- [51] Alfè, D. & Gillan, M. J. First-principles calculation of transport coefficients. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **81**, 5161–5164 (1998).

- [52] Jackson Kimball, D. F., Boyd, A. & Budker, D. Constraints on anomalous spin-spin interactions from spin-exchange collisions. *Phys. Rev. A* **82**, 062714 (2010).
- [53] Kimball, D. F. J. *et al.* A dual-isotope rubidium comagnetometer to search for anomalous long-range spin-mass (spin-gravity) couplings of the proton. *Annalen der Physik* **525**, 514–528 (2013).
- [54] Brown, J. M., Smullin, S. J., Kornack, T. W. & Romalis, M. V. New limit on lorentz- and *cpt*-violating neutron spin interactions. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **105**, 151604 (2010).
- [55] Harris, R. *Modern Physics* (Pearson/Addison Wesley, 2008).
- [56] Stein, D. *A Test of Special Relativity - Pushing down the Limits on a Possible Violation of Local Lorentz Invariance*. Bachelor's thesis, Amherst College, Amherst, MA (2006).
- [57] Steck, D. A. Cesium d line data. *Los Alamos National Laboratory (unpublished)* **124** (2003).
- [58] Happer, W. Optical pumping. *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **44**, 169–249 (1972).
- [59] Sagle, J., Namiotka, R. & Huennekens, J. Measurement and modelling of intensity dependent absorption and transit relaxation on the cesium line. *Journal of Physics B: Atomic, Molecular and Optical Physics* **29**, 2629 (1996).

- [60] Bell, W. E. & Bloom, A. L. Optical detection of magnetic resonance in alkali metal vapor. *Phys. Rev.* **107**, 1559–1565 (1957).
- [61] Budker, D. & Kimball, D. *Optical Magnetometry*. Optical Magnetometry (Cambridge University Press, 2013).
- [62] Jackson, J. *Classical Electrodynamics* (Wiley, 1998).
- [63] Hummon, M. *The Search for Violations of Local Lorentz Invariance Using Hg and Cs Magnetometers*. Bachelor’s thesis, Amherst College, Amherst, MA (2002).
- [64] Foss, A. *Measuring a Violation of Local Lorentz Invariance*. Bachelor’s thesis, Amherst College, Amherst, MA (2003).
- [65] Orbaker, D. *Spinning the Spins: Constructing a Rotating Apparatus to Set New Limits on Local Lorentz Invariance*. Bachelor’s thesis, Amherst College, Amherst, MA (2004).
- [66] Kim, D.-K. *A Search for Local Lorentz Violation*. Bachelor’s thesis, Amherst College, Amherst, MA (2008).
- [67] Heckel, B. R. *et al.* Preferred-frame and *cp*-violation tests with polarized electrons. *Phys. Rev. D* **78**, 092006 (2008).
- [68] Mathur, B., Tang, H. & Happer, W. Light shifts in the alkali atoms. *Physical Review* **171**, 11 (1968).
- [69] Happer, W. & Mathur, B. S. Effective operator formalism in optical pumping. *Phys. Rev.* **163**, 12–25 (1967).

- [70] Budker, D., Kimball, D. & DeMille, D. *Atomic Physics: An Exploration Through Problems and Solutions* (Oxford University Press, 2004).
- [71] Murthy, S. A., Krause, D., Li, Z. L. & Hunter, L. R. New limits on the electron electric dipole moment from cesium. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **63**, 965–968 (1989).
- [72] Balabas, M. V., Karaulanov, T., Ledbetter, M. P. & Budker, D. Polarized alkali-metal vapor with minute-long transverse spin-relaxation time. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **105**, 070801 (2010).
- [73] Teng, C. *Frequency Control and Stabilization of a Laser System*. Bachelor's thesis, Amherst College, Amherst, MA (2013).
- [74] Vaughan, M. *The Fabry-Perot Interferometer: History, Theory, Practice and Applications*. Series in Optics and Optoelectronics (Taylor & Francis, 1989).
- [75] Araki, M. Pid control. *Control systems, robotics and automation* **2**, 1–23 (2002).
- [76] Stanford Research Systems. *About Lock-In Amplifiers: Application Note #3*.